

$\frac{d^9}{dx^9} u(x, z) = \frac{1}{dx^9 dz^2} (\dots)$

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$\frac{d^9}{dx^9 dz^2} u(x, z) = \frac{1}{dx^9 dz^2} (\dots)$

"... Derivative Order: 7 - x != 1 ..."

21	1 + 21	2 + 21
1	1 + 21	2 + 1
0	1	2

$\frac{d^7}{dx^7} u(x,z) = \frac{1}{dx^7} (\dots)$

$\frac{d^7}{dx^7} u(x,z) = \frac{1}{dx^7} (\dots)$

$\frac{d^7}{dx^7} u(x,z) = \frac{1}{dx^7} (\dots)$

$\frac{d^4}{dx^4} u(x,z) = \frac{1}{dx^4} (\dots)$

$\frac{d^4}{dx^4} u(x,z) = \frac{1}{dx^4} (\dots)$

"... Derivative Order: 8 - x != 1 ..."

21	1 + 21	2 + 21
1	1 + 21	2 + 1
0	1	2

$\frac{d^8}{dx^8} u(x,z) = \frac{1}{dx^8} (\dots)$

$\frac{d^4}{dx^4} u(x,z) = \frac{1}{dx^4} (\dots)$

$\frac{d^4}{dx^4} u(x,z) = \frac{1}{dx^4} (\dots)$

$\frac{d^7}{dx^7} u(x, z) = \frac{1}{dx^7 dz^2} (\dots)$

"... Derivative Order: 8 - x != 1 ..."

21	1 + 21	2 + 21
1	1 + 21	2 + 1
0	1	2

$\frac{d^8}{dx^8} u(x,z) = \frac{1}{dx^8} (\dots)$

$\frac{d^6}{dx^6} u(x,z) = \frac{1}{dx^6} (\dots)$

"... Derivative Order: 1 - x != 1 ..."

11	1 + 31	2 + 31	3 + 31
21	1 + 21	2 + 31	3 + 21
1	1 + 2 + 1	2 + 1	3 + 1
0	1	2	3

$\frac{d^6}{dx^6} u(x,z) = \frac{1}{dx^6} (\dots)$

$\frac{d^6}{dx^6} u(x,z) = \frac{1}{dx^6} (\dots)$

"... Derivative Order: 1 - x != 1 ..."

11	1 + 31	2 + 31	3 + 31
21	1 + 21	2 + 31	3 + 21
1	1 + 2 + 1	2 + 1	3 + 1
0	1	2	3

$\frac{d^6}{dx^6} u(x,z) = \frac{1}{dx^6} (\dots)$

[-275898187850080571675125224 + 102928737806463671436814694304] u_{n+1} + ... (12922140957128079925805734880 - 675870990180039866548387296) u_{n+1} + ...

[-5031046933302707429549492 - 13867537852289008872416] u_{n+1} + ... (-1009576864538854952034546 + 1022364878780512284847848552104) u_{n+1} + ... (1352618726497832860121425247236 - 507515715341941997056011424) u_{n+1} + ...

[10542178121015361263457509716] u_{n+1} + ... (666244092324956898978784 - 171903171889195695820342820) u_{n+1} + ... (-138265493390848014573290416) u_{n+1} + ... (-137268058589537220088404 + 4365366710526401492139088) u_{n+1} + ...

[-718208430471553848926471174464] u_{n+1} + ... (642756237402106567429282904048 - 286079388878125062472371948552) u_{n+1} + ... (-2537914989683994581820783896 + 33802853828737011896304812192) u_{n+1} + ...

+ [-189478026260858329852306 + 394706845653158350888004] u_{n+1} + ... (268219519369742664368600716 + 379529554582752596619044) u_{n+1} + ... (7305187101004360167118376) u_{n+1} + ...

+ [-267378197544259169771374424 + 1556613318823179701520] u_{n+1} + ... (-3448727201181736198795464 - 4792732106181736198795464) u_{n+1} + ... (24851528265867268766879216 + 18260490947868338904004) u_{n+1} + ...

+ [-255073197280049959741575801] u_{n+1} + ... (-679621891661801376197355088 + 5401325460592148272725512) u_{n+1} + ... (-245761672440755918302271284 + 7037974617055918302271284) u_{n+1} + ...

+ [-189478026260858329852306 + 394706845653158350888004] u_{n+1} + ... (-142315442325271640670966 + 2646544170551562183254272) u_{n+1} + ... (-39011446631920771291594542 + 13867537852289008872416) u_{n+1} + ...

+ [-189478026260858329852306 + 394706845653158350888004] u_{n+1} + ... (-501815894661970121000 + 907313245927163330000) u_{n+1} + ... (86237962640413932675600 + 12366064917683381090000) u_{n+1} + ...

+ [-28073597516932929216 + 52625567488872664920] u_{n+1} + ... (14946183699096538256 + 19838783165545367072) u_{n+1} + ... (18578780090806043184 - 15225792823819883600) u_{n+1}, Q(d^2), Quadant I

Derivative Order: 6, x1 = ...
1 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1
2 1 + 1 + 2 + 2 + 1 + 3 + 2 + 1
3 1 + 1 + 2 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 1
0 1 2 3
Error order, 11, Error, 1.222557508685977191 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.717839509911681871 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.71783950991681873 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.717837848262149499 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.7178347884262194499 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.71783783700144927 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.7178347837047359762 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.71783783700144927 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.717834783700144927 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.717834783700144927 * 10^-10

130 d^3
Error order, 11, Error, 1.222557508685977191 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.717839509911681871 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.71783950991681873 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.717837848262149499 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.7178347884262194499 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.71783783700144927 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.7178347837047359762 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.71783783700144927 * 10^-10

1/2000 d^5
Error order, 11, Error, 1.222557508685977191 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.717839509911681871 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.71783950991681873 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.717837848262149499 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.7178347884262194499 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.71783783700144927 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.7178347837047359762 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.71783783700144927 * 10^-10

1/16000 d^6
Error order, 11, Error, 1.222557508685977191 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.717839509911681871 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.71783950991681873 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.717837848262149499 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.7178347884262194499 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.71783783700144927 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.7178347837047359762 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.71783783700144927 * 10^-10

1/2190000 d^7
Error order, 11, Error, 1.222557508685977191 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.717839509911681871 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.71783950991681873 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.717837848262149499 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.7178347884262194499 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.71783783700144927 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.7178347837047359762 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.71783783700144927 * 10^-10

Derivative Order: 7, x1 = ...
1 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1
2 1 + 1 + 2 + 2 + 1 + 3 + 2 + 1
3 1 + 1 + 2 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 1
0 1 2 3
Error order, 11, Error, 1.8740822662681298 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.86382546514281554 * 10^-10
Error order, 10, Error, 1.86382546514281554 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.863817909097519577 * 10^-10
Error order, 10, Error, 1.863817909097519577 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.863817909097519577 * 10^-10
Error order, 10, Error, 1.8638179091526156909 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.8638179091526156909 * 10^-10

1/7600000 d^8
Error order, 11, Error, 1.222557508685977191 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.717839509911681871 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.71783950991681873 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.717837848262149499 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.7178347884262194499 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.71783783700144927 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.7178347837047359762 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.71783783700144927 * 10^-10

1/76000000 d^9
Error order, 11, Error, 1.222557508685977191 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.717839509911681871 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.71783950991681873 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.717837848262149499 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.7178347884262194499 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.71783783700144927 * 10^-10
Error order, 11, Error, 1.7178347837047359762 * 10^-10, New Error, 1.71783783700144927 * 10^-10

-- Derivative Order: 1, x=1 --"

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} 41 & + & 41 & + & 2 & + & 41 & + & 3 & + & 41 & + & 4 & + & 1 \\ 31 & + & 3 & + & 21 & + &; 3 & + & 3 & + & 41 & + & 3 & + & 1 \\ 21 & + & 1 & + & 2 & + & 1 & + & 2 & + & 1 & + & 2 & + & 1 \\ 1 & + & 1 & + & 2 & + & 1 & + & 3 & + & 4 & + & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & \end{array}$$

1/3	16	-16	2081	17	-17	17	-18	+36	208	-144	1	-1	8	
6/3	-161	544	-1632	4860	-7340	13	2720	-2720	144	2081	3	25	-25	
9/3	16	-16	4896	-9792	-29835	+29831	73	-48960	13	13	13	13	-36	+18
12/3	-16	-48	1	2720	-2720	1	9792	-4896	1632	-544	1	2081	18	17
15/3	-237961	+237961	48	+161	-90	-48	+161	-90	-48	+161	-90	-48	+161	
18/3	44200	44200												

Error order: 24, Error: 8.476310322340552917 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 8.443949416582251042 × 10⁻⁵⁵
 Error order: 24, Error: 8.443939416582251042 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 8.4439701189819000 × 10⁻⁵⁵
 Error order: 24, Error: 8.44390703189819003 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 8.443970048103416608 × 10⁻⁵⁵
 Error order: 24, Error: 8.443907048103416608 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 8.443907047816232307 × 10⁻⁵⁵
 Error order: 24, Error: 8.443907047816232307 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 8.443907687181295513 × 10⁻⁵⁵

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{8791380000 \cdot x^4} \left(-5496251200 u_{x+1} + 5378256000 u_{x+2} - 4137120000 u_{x+3} + \dots + 132600 u_{x+24} \right)$$

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{8791380000 \cdot x^4} \left(-5496251200 u_{x+1} + 5378256000 u_{x+2} - 4137120000 u_{x+3} + 132600 u_{x+24} \right)$$

Error order: 24, Error: 1.691892416054002578 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 1.685470492180149729 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 1.685470492180149729 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 1.685410582644931 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 1.685410582644931 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 1.68541057900253225 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 1.68541057900253225 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 1.6854105799640035 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 1.6854105799640035 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 1.68541057960339234 × 10⁻⁵⁰

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{116573698800000 \cdot x^4} \left(-1824464047500 u_{x+1} + 2057182920000 u_{x+2} + 2674337960000 u_{x+3} + \dots + 132600 u_{x+24} \right)$$

Error order: 24, Error: 2.523773862356291285 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 2.523079414997284025 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 2.523079414997284025 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 2.523069739918328824 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 2.523069739918328824 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 2.5230697326286451 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 2.5230697326286451 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 2.5230697323593193 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 2.5230697323593193 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 2.52306973203583176 × 10⁻⁵⁰

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{72838323064516250000 \cdot x^4} \left(30197065251562500 u_{x+1} + 59102869291600000 u_{x+2} + 454674252000000 u_{x+3} + \dots + 132600 u_{x+24} \right)$$

Error order: 24, Error: 2.523079414997284025 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 2.523079414997284025 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 2.523069739918328824 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 2.523069739918328824 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 2.5230697326286451 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 2.5230697326286451 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 2.5230697323593193 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 2.5230697323593193 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 2.52306973203583176 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 2.52306973203583176 × 10⁻⁵⁰

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{72838323064516250000 \cdot x^4} \left(30197065251562500 u_{x+1} + 59102869291600000 u_{x+2} + 454674252000000 u_{x+3} + \dots + 132600 u_{x+24} \right)$$

Error order: 24, Error: 2.523079414997284025 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 2.523079414997284025 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 2.523069739918328824 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 2.523069739918328824 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 2.5230697326286451 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 2.5230697326286451 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 2.5230697323593193 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 2.5230697323593193 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 2.52306973203583176 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 2.52306973203583176 × 10⁻⁵⁰

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{72838323064516250000 \cdot x^4} \left(30197065251562500 u_{x+1} + 59102869291600000 u_{x+2} + 454674252000000 u_{x+3} + \dots + 132600 u_{x+24} \right)$$

Error order: 24, Error: 3.370290212450148737 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 3.357391044537969428 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 3.357391044537969428 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 3.35738200975628097 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 3.35738200975628097 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 3.3573821222344789 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 3.3573821222344789 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 3.3573821222344789 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 3.3573821222344789 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 3.3573821222344789 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 3.3573821222344789 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 3.3573821222344789 × 10⁻⁵⁰

-- Derivative Order: 2, x=1 --"

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} 41 & + & 41 & + & 2 & + & 41 & + & 3 & + & 41 & + & 4 \\ 31 & + & 3 & + & 21 & + & 3 & + & 3 & + & 41 & + & 3 \\ 21 & + & 2 & + & 21 & + & 2 & + & 1 & + & 2 & + & 1 & + & 2 \\ 1 & + & 2 & + & 2 & + & 1 & + & 3 & + & 4 & + & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & \end{array}$$

28091	237961	75148	666384	202239	6265927	757232	40763761	581091
18640	8840	525	525	525	525	525	525	
172888	11245281	352496	40259921	1237384	12727744	11086828	75732	
16575	49275	325	325	65	13	585	2765	
1942749	21416491	15223752	488536561	612659971	12727744	2023939	62659271	
2210	2210	325	325	10	65	13	1050	
327678	2808891	3453751	15223752	48853656	324496	74025921	75148	
525	525	325	325	325	325	325	325	
1123052691	3276975	20894881	1942749	21416491	172688	112452381	28091	
1898000	525	525	2210	2210	16575	49275	8840	

Error order: 23, Error: 6.453657128420140849 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 6.42906286315020423 × 10⁻⁵⁵
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.42906286315020423 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{79122400000 \cdot x^4} \left(-520106405000 u_{x+1} + 109481863135775 u_{x+2} + 154058242726400 u_{x+3} + \dots + 132600 u_{x+24} \right)$$

Error order: 23, Error: 6.453657128420140849 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 6.42906286315020423 × 10⁻⁵⁵
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.42906286315020423 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{79122400000 \cdot x^4} \left(-520106405000 u_{x+1} + 109481863135775 u_{x+2} + 154058242726400 u_{x+3} + \dots + 132600 u_{x+24} \right)$$

Error order: 23, Error: 1.28667852484059125 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 1.28667852484059125 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 23, Error: 1.28667852484059125 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 1.28667852484059125 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 23, Error: 1.28667852484059125 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 1.28667852484059125 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 23, Error: 1.28667852484059125 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 1.28667852484059125 × 10⁻⁵⁰
 Error order: 23, Error: 1.28667852484059125 × 10⁻⁵⁰, New Error: 1.28667852484059125 × 10⁻⁵⁰

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{79122400000 \cdot x^4} \left(-520106405000 u_{x+1} + 109481863135775 u_{x+2} + 154058242726400 u_{x+3} + \dots + 132600 u_{x+24} \right)$$

Error order: 23, Error: 6.453657128420140849 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 6.42906286315020423 × 10⁻⁵⁵
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.42906286315020423 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵, New Error: 6.4289725922137911 × 10⁻⁵⁵

51 1 + 51 2 + 51 3 + 51 4 + 51 5 + 51
41 1 + 41 2 + 41 3 + 41 4 + 41 5 + 41
31 1 + 31 2 + 31 3 + 31 4 + 31 5 + 31
21 1 + 21 2 + 21 3 + 21 4 + 21 5 + 21
1 1 + 2 1 3 4 5
0 1 2 3 4 5

Table with numerical values and indices. Columns contain various numbers such as 1010718027, 173639919573, 32259963607529, etc. Some columns are labeled with $u_{i,j}$ and α .

$\frac{d^\alpha}{dx^\alpha} u(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} u(t) dt$ (170844899565808 - 2302399933579800) $u_{i,j+1} + (-34686001838106259900 + 1307297360713644500) u_{i,j+2} + (-54360030192231533600 + 442265206271252563200) u_{i,j+3} + \dots$
+ (-9931259653286280400 + 2920311657008912000) $u_{i,j+4} + (-25224591122337344800 + 74713476132782830400) u_{i,j+5} + \dots$
+ 6026249474659514761000 $u_{i,j+6} + (-15192906878025844096984 + 33697701885792228916288) u_{i,j+7} + \dots$
+ (74713476132782830400 - 25224591122337344800 + 1307297360713644500 - 405492940906632575) $u_{i,j+8} + (-2302399933579800 + 710844899565808) u_{i,j+9}$. $\mathcal{O}(dx^{\alpha})$. *Quadrat I*

... Derivative Order: 4 x - 1 - ...
51 1 + 51 2 + 51 3 + 51 4 + 51 5 + 51
41 1 + 41 2 + 41 3 + 41 4 + 41 5 + 41
31 1 + 31 2 + 31 3 + 31 4 + 31 5 + 31
21 1 + 21 2 + 21 3 + 21 4 + 21 5 + 21
1 1 + 2 1 3 4 5
0 1 2 3 4 5

Table with numerical values and indices, similar to the first table. Columns contain various numbers such as 1029994532485983, 22619180371477071, 76784274136225927, etc. Some columns are labeled with $u_{i,j}$ and α .

$\frac{d^\alpha}{dx^\alpha} u(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} u(t) dt$ (455257583422804486 + 4998838862096432470) $u_{i,j+1} + (497109778188546825250 - 102041848908716384700) u_{i,j+2} + (-7943248093800160372200 + 10341437782025187132600) u_{i,j+3} + \dots$
+ 81210912460847141550 $u_{i,j+4} + (-9630862713606700650200 + 20766736246509976103400) u_{i,j+5} + (-139113808230405497266728 + 52719209664653112899584) u_{i,j+6} + \dots$
+ 37380132805681676509604 $u_{i,j+7} + (-7943248093800160372200 + 10341437782025187132600) u_{i,j+8} + (4357848743834419590550 + 2035869537372712393950) u_{i,j+9} + \dots$
+ 23211680220984091000 $u_{i,j+10} + (455257583422804486 + 4998838862096432470) u_{i,j+11}$. $\mathcal{O}(dx^{\alpha})$. *Quadrat I*

... Derivative Order: 5 x - 1 - ...
51 1 + 51 2 + 51 3 + 51 4 + 51 5 + 51
41 1 + 41 2 + 41 3 + 41 4 + 41 5 + 41
31 1 + 31 2 + 31 3 + 31 4 + 31 5 + 31
21 1 + 21 2 + 21 3 + 21 4 + 21 5 + 21
1 1 + 2 1 3 4 5
0 1 2 3 4 5

Table with numerical values and indices, similar to the first table. Columns contain various numbers such as 326843341817846419, 1029994532485983, 468963585106075893, etc. Some columns are labeled with $u_{i,j}$ and α .

$\frac{d^\alpha}{dx^\alpha} u(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} u(t) dt$ (-144664757083481179 + 9105151666845089927) $u_{i,j+1} + (7628086529737323625 + 2301782398100619458775) u_{i,j+2} + (27570148290895139075200 + 384803132845326514660) u_{i,j+3} + \dots$
+ (68055670232320413261675 - 489015625702320413261675) $u_{i,j+4} + (18384548513761981343000 + 516656542511687213650) u_{i,j+5} + (450405018779011486222400 + 17828410250930751933800) u_{i,j+6} + \dots$
+ (5676031420318661889925500 - 5676031420318661889925500) $u_{i,j+7} + (3742722559177996982745600 + 53381687199854151495432900) u_{i,j+8} + (-2071051705198355400212288 + 97276342661774046555084) u_{i,j+9} + \dots$
+ (9241583437035967319 - 9241583437035967319) $u_{i,j+10} + (-277468133404962999400 + 9206267077136708646250) u_{i,j+11} + (-18628893950939666449100 + 8542057081824461444200) u_{i,j+12} + (-17824810254090579353800 + 450440818079011486223100) u_{i,j+13} + \dots$
+ (2455178292722506875 - 1841186720024848301975) $u_{i,j+14} + (9105151666845089927 + 14444075703888117198) u_{i,j+15}$. $\mathcal{O}(dx^{\alpha})$. *Quadrat I*

... Derivative Order: 6 x - 1 - ...
51 1 + 51 2 + 51 3 + 51 4 + 51 5 + 51
41 1 + 41 2 + 41 3 + 41 4 + 41 5 + 41
31 1 + 31 2 + 31 3 + 31 4 + 31 5 + 31
21 1 + 21 2 + 21 3 + 21 4 + 21 5 + 21
1 1 + 2 1 3 4 5
0 1 2 3 4 5

Table with numerical values and indices, similar to the first table. Columns contain various numbers such as 414051218194180087, 352805278856419011, 9147623187801303641, etc. Some columns are labeled with $u_{i,j}$ and α .

$\frac{d^\alpha}{dx^\alpha} u(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} u(t) dt$ (9105519204931958347 - 796935866271450121) $u_{i,j+1} + (-17837865216366245209950 + 9249422992942608907950) u_{i,j+2} + (-18517193531270035348900 + 137362939001245200113300) u_{i,j+3} + (-119025586198257528100 + 2132242405093879509300) u_{i,j+4} + \dots$
+ (1392767670000 - 696633380000) $u_{i,j+5} + (11270000 - 11270000) u_{i,j+6} + (14386814822279401535 + 72052941857754942175) u_{i,j+7} + (-83170881254730617919314552200 - 85170881254730617919314552200) u_{i,j+8} + \dots$
+ (4267815600800872197400 - 356540310049012378155950) $u_{i,j+9} + (36862924529269703657100 + 148392451058680245976030100) u_{i,j+10} + (-3080286753990763917825 + 2518453043266913872925) u_{i,j+11} + (-9150319204931998347 + 796935866271450121) u_{i,j+12}$. $\mathcal{O}(dx^{\alpha})$. *Quadrat I*

... Derivative Order: 7 x - 1 - ...
51 1 + 51 2 + 51 3 + 51 4 + 51 5 + 51
41 1 + 41 2 + 41 3 + 41 4 + 41 5 + 41
31 1 + 31 2 + 31 3 + 31 4 + 31 5 + 31
21 1 + 21 2 + 21 3 + 21 4 + 21 5 + 21
1 1 + 2 1 3 4 5
0 1 2 3 4 5

Table with numerical values and indices, similar to the first table. Columns contain various numbers such as 24696176951995023307, 253797191629325133071, 203524036404576843809, etc. Some columns are labeled with $u_{i,j}$ and α .

$\frac{d^\alpha}{dx^\alpha} u(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} u(t) dt$ (7 (-18345714500345458852 + 1883505663895008852) $u_{i,j+1} + (3023785683275146748800 - 9155470956371102757900) u_{i,j+2} + (56247860939171623201200 - 35794196929735935904400) u_{i,j+3} + (2234318752378139516400 + 250678817415355554772800) u_{i,j+4} + (-24062908530485148744500 + 79476215466057673500) u_{i,j+5} + (95012744328761493325 + 95012744328761493325) u_{i,j+6} + (-308213912204899310875 + 21561405782995335325) u_{i,j+7} + (54571962894089526186000 - 160000186826146268102100) u_{i,j+8} + (264977526794937182970576 - 12967309997794421763210668) u_{i,j+9} + (-1752765552487668854576) u_{i,j+10} + (-20746094468153887307500 - 4780875394562612502400) u_{i,j+11} + (-243779050509326570577168 + 4535066847361504668119542576) u_{i,j+12} + (-71052279428757173720639102000 + 71052279428757173720639102000) u_{i,j+13} + (67378496651138864947898000 - 48423700071653989162000) u_{i,j+14} + (12967999973704432106678125 + 2649775261794371782970576) u_{i,j+15} + (-35794196929735935904400 + 56247752676164371023500) u_{i,j+16} + (-18345714500345458852 + 1883505663895008852) u_{i,j+17} + (-10765320652204400928500 + 850274408682254621000) u_{i,j+18} + (-56212266464818034001000 + 2466494338451805400) u_{i,j+19} + (-10765320652204400928500 + 850274408682254621000) u_{i,j+20}$. $\mathcal{O}(dx^{\alpha})$. *Quadrat I*

Error order: 29, Error: 6.64832837479368230 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 6.648296313930377073 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰

Error order: 29, Error: 6.648296313930377073 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 6.648296281899249016 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰

Error order: 29, Error: 6.648296281899249016 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 6.648296281837531616 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰

Error order: 29, Error: 6.648296281837531616 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 6.648296281837499555 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰

... Derivative Order: 8 - x!-1 ...

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of numbers, likely representing a derivative or binomial coefficients.

Large table with 10 columns and 10 rows of numerical data, possibly representing a matrix or a set of coefficients.

u(x) = 1 / (1283390072900000 * ad^21) * ((-88733813624193503550 + 118793295889254773950 u_{x+1} + ...)

+ 19942725780511262975928360 u_{x+2} + 952598267692594466929031449 u_{x+3} + ...

+ 36212653112574239351659443640 u_{x+4} + 74095795495362635546657541980 u_{x+5} + ...

+ 20831148197448952821056 u_{x+6} + 773549942140904314625 u_{x+7} + ...

... Derivative Order: 9 - x!-1 ...

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of numbers, similar to the previous derivative table.

Large table with 10 columns and 10 rows of numerical data, similar to the previous table.

u(x) = 1 / (1283390072900000 * ad^21) * (21 (266682458800629981620 + 354934325452967740420 u_{x+1} + ...)

+ 2464363781471857198279690120 u_{x+2} + (-12564561904150010781690419 + 125644561904150010781690419 u_{x+1} + ...)

+ 113054538097688654272044 u_{x+3} + 59433818523150043602469991320 + 338620730511028249819930880 u_{x+4} + ...

+ 2590651550742357809792830 u_{x+5} + 82455580281901331254679406 + 2209031770732662997297956 u_{x+6} + ...

... Derivative Order: 10 - x!-1 ...

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of numbers, similar to the previous derivative tables.

Large table with 10 columns and 10 rows of numerical data, similar to the previous tables.

u(x) = 1 / (1283390072900000 * ad^21) * ((-1721940312083193730767 + 126359068542869247977 u_{x+1} + ...)

+ 169284891973120389647691812 u_{x+2} + 141796830638681255264673064 u_{x+3} + ...

+ 134085430803072093061669580 u_{x+4} + 100938049156054537881909375120 u_{x+5} + ...

+ 1798257860939495973582 u_{x+6} + 899835810712265385260641 u_{x+7} + ...

... Derivative Order: 11 - x!-1 ...

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of numbers, similar to the previous derivative tables.

Large table with 10 columns and 10 rows of numerical data, similar to the previous tables.

u(x) = 1 / (12633968542486924797 - 72764177950388344795297 u_{x+1} + ...)

+ 6802682632990104667311036 - 757544416356208078961384148 u_{x+2} + 346025797286941368976364485 u_{x+3} + ...

+ 29205235613476706803840 + 20773456701469346553992201 u_{x+4} + 918892149811454243895826148 - 1529509209591473877109937036 u_{x+5} + ...

+ 730748526230966386712159036 + 1254064556681585132953899648 u_{x+6} + 59440946587994251588172785 - 2485203321370791975211085 u_{x+7} + ...

... Derivative Order: 12 - x!-1 ...

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of numbers, similar to the previous derivative tables.

Large table with 10 columns and 10 rows of numerical data, similar to the previous tables.

u(x) = 1/327 [2079 (-1126771070020194500 + 18934712863917966600) u_{x+1} + ...] Q(x, dx^2), Quadrant I

Error order: 24, Error: 7.348990036654879098 x 10^-10, New Error: 7.119709927294201471 x 10^-10

... Derivative Order: 13 - x! - 1 ...

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of integers: 5 1 1 + 5 1 2 + 5 1 3 + 5 1 4 + 5 1 5 + 1

Large table with 10 columns and 10 rows of numerical values, likely representing a grid of data points or coefficients.

u(x) = 1/37910250000 dx^14 [2079 (-23625439813483388810 + 51078042801400877800) u_{x+1} + ...] Q(x, dx^2), Quadrant I

Error order: 23, Error: 7.11934061441000339 x 10^-10, New Error: 7.119340244732783406 x 10^-10

... Derivative Order: 14 - x! - 1 ...

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of integers: 5 1 1 + 5 1 2 + 5 1 3 + 5 1 4 + 5 1 5 + 1

Large table with 10 columns and 10 rows of numerical values, similar to the previous table.

u(x) = 1/189850025000 dx^14 [4553 (-9612758499818010395 - 590087743306848193) u_{x+1} + ...] Q(x, dx^2), Quadrant I

Error order: 23, Error: 7.11934061441000339 x 10^-10, New Error: 7.119340244732783406 x 10^-10

... Derivative Order: 15 - x! - 1 ...

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of integers: 5 1 1 + 5 1 2 + 5 1 3 + 5 1 4 + 5 1 5 + 1

Large table with 10 columns and 10 rows of numerical values, similar to the previous tables.

u(x) = 1/4936115665000 dx^14 [4369 (-15363628125958205018 + 58665224661465740518) u_{x+1} + ...] Q(x, dx^2), Quadrant I

Error order: 22, Error: 9.264415204001437424 x 10^-10, New Error: 9.22238092292062486281 x 10^-10

... Derivative Order: 16 - x! - 1 ...

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of integers: 5 1 1 + 5 1 2 + 5 1 3 + 5 1 4 + 5 1 5 + 1

Large table with 10 columns and 10 rows of numerical values, similar to the previous tables.

u(x) = 1/14517987250 dx^14 [4369 (-5086287428783776150 + 916173160251611150) u_{x+1} + ...] Q(x, dx^2), Quadrant I

Error order: 20, Error: 9.0244168877691513 x 10^-10, New Error: 9.0224108877691513 x 10^-10

... Derivative Order: 17 - x! - 1 ...

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of integers: 5 1 1 + 5 1 2 + 5 1 3 + 5 1 4 + 5 1 5 + 1

Large table with 10 columns and 10 rows of numerical values, similar to the previous tables.

u(x) = 1 / (17856794793373445000) ...

u(x) = 1 / (60263638080740 + 6151704769700490) ...

u(x) = 1 / (25921300074000) ...

Table with 6 columns and 6 rows of numerical values.

Table with 6 columns and 6 rows of numerical values, including a central 3x3 grid.

u(x) = 1 / (60263638080740 + 6151704769700490) ...

u(x) = 1 / (1047801023008000) ...

Table with 6 columns and 6 rows of numerical values.

Table with 6 columns and 6 rows of numerical values, including a central 3x3 grid.

u(x) = 1 / (1047801023008000) ...

Table with 6 columns and 6 rows of numerical values.

Table with 6 columns and 6 rows of numerical values, including a central 3x3 grid.

Table with 6 columns and 6 rows of numerical values.

u(x) = 1 / (1061705994180000000) ...

u(x) = 1 / (1061705994180000000) ...

Table with 6 columns and 6 rows of numerical values.

Table with 10 columns of numerical data, likely representing a grid of values for a mathematical function or model. The values are small integers and floating-point numbers.

Table with 10 columns of numerical data, continuing the grid from the previous table. It includes some larger integers and floating-point numbers.

Derivative Order: 10 - k-1 - m
Error order, 38. Error, 1.91171042614732518 x 10^-10. New Error, 1.900588383195493826 x 10^-10
Error order, 40. Error, 1.900588383195493826 x 10^-10. New Error, 1.900588383195493826 x 10^-10
Error order, 42. Error, 1.900588383195493826 x 10^-10. New Error, 1.900588383195493826 x 10^-10
Error order, 44. Error, 1.900588383195493826 x 10^-10. New Error, 1.900588383195493826 x 10^-10
Error order, 46. Error, 1.900588383195493826 x 10^-10. New Error, 1.900588383195493826 x 10^-10

Table with 10 columns of numerical data, including some larger integers and floating-point numbers. It appears to be a continuation of the grid data.

Table with 10 columns of numerical data, including some larger integers and floating-point numbers. It appears to be a continuation of the grid data.

Derivative Order: 11 - k-1 - m
Error order, 38. Error, 9.9022663494283988 x 10^-10. New Error, 9.84441487158135557 x 10^-10
Error order, 39. Error, 9.84441837185315557 x 10^-10. New Error, 9.84453793413225957 x 10^-10
Error order, 40. Error, 9.84453793413225957 x 10^-10. New Error, 9.84453793413225957 x 10^-10
Error order, 41. Error, 9.84453793413225957 x 10^-10. New Error, 9.84453793413225957 x 10^-10
Error order, 42. Error, 9.84453793413225957 x 10^-10. New Error, 9.84453793413225957 x 10^-10

Table with 10 columns of numerical data, including some larger integers and floating-point numbers. It appears to be a continuation of the grid data.

Table with 10 columns of numerical data, including some larger integers and floating-point numbers. It appears to be a continuation of the grid data.

Derivative Order: 12 - k-1 - m
Error order, 38. Error, 4.95176695270827787 x 10^-10. New Error, 4.9164236868685523 x 10^-10
Error order, 39. Error, 4.9164236868685523 x 10^-10. New Error, 4.9164236868685523 x 10^-10
Error order, 40. Error, 4.9164236868685523 x 10^-10. New Error, 4.9164236868685523 x 10^-10
Error order, 41. Error, 4.9164236868685523 x 10^-10. New Error, 4.9164236868685523 x 10^-10
Error order, 42. Error, 4.9164236868685523 x 10^-10. New Error, 4.9164236868685523 x 10^-10

Table with 10 columns of numerical data, including some larger integers and floating-point numbers. It appears to be a continuation of the grid data.

Derivative Order: 13 - k-1 - m
Error order, 38. Error, 2.4758735000000000 x 10^-10. New Error, 2.4758735000000000 x 10^-10
Error order, 39. Error, 2.4758735000000000 x 10^-10. New Error, 2.4758735000000000 x 10^-10
Error order, 40. Error, 2.4758735000000000 x 10^-10. New Error, 2.4758735000000000 x 10^-10
Error order, 41. Error, 2.4758735000000000 x 10^-10. New Error, 2.4758735000000000 x 10^-10
Error order, 42. Error, 2.4758735000000000 x 10^-10. New Error, 2.4758735000000000 x 10^-10

Table with 10 columns of numerical data, including some larger integers and floating-point numbers. It appears to be a continuation of the grid data.

Derivative Order: 14 - k-1 - m
Error order, 38. Error, 1.2379367500000000 x 10^-10. New Error, 1.2379367500000000 x 10^-10
Error order, 39. Error, 1.2379367500000000 x 10^-10. New Error, 1.2379367500000000 x 10^-10
Error order, 40. Error, 1.2379367500000000 x 10^-10. New Error, 1.2379367500000000 x 10^-10
Error order, 41. Error, 1.2379367500000000 x 10^-10. New Error, 1.2379367500000000 x 10^-10
Error order, 42. Error, 1.2379367500000000 x 10^-10. New Error, 1.2379367500000000 x 10^-10

Table with 10 columns of numerical data, including some larger integers and floating-point numbers. It appears to be a continuation of the grid data.

Derivative Order: 15 - k-1 - m
Error order, 38. Error, 6.1875000000000000 x 10^-11. New Error, 6.1875000000000000 x 10^-11
Error order, 39. Error, 6.1875000000000000 x 10^-11. New Error, 6.1875000000000000 x 10^-11
Error order, 40. Error, 6.1875000000000000 x 10^-11. New Error, 6.1875000000000000 x 10^-11
Error order, 41. Error, 6.1875000000000000 x 10^-11. New Error, 6.1875000000000000 x 10^-11
Error order, 42. Error, 6.1875000000000000 x 10^-11. New Error, 6.1875000000000000 x 10^-11

Mathematical expressions for u(x) and Q(x) involving various coefficients and indices.

Derivative order 10, x = -1, -1 + 31, -1 + 31 - 2 + 31, etc. Includes a table of coefficients and error analysis.

Derivative order 10, x = 1, -1 + 31, -1 + 31 - 2 + 31, etc. Includes a table of coefficients and error analysis.

Derivative order 9, x = -1, -1 + 31, -1 + 31 - 2 + 31, etc. Includes a table of coefficients and error analysis.

Derivative order 9, x = 1, -1 + 31, -1 + 31 - 2 + 31, etc. Includes a table of coefficients and error analysis.

Derivative order 8, x = -1, -1 + 31, -1 + 31 - 2 + 31, etc. Includes a table of coefficients and error analysis.

Derivative order 8, x = 1, -1 + 31, -1 + 31 - 2 + 31, etc. Includes a table of coefficients and error analysis.

Derivative order 7, x = -1, -1 + 31, -1 + 31 - 2 + 31, etc. Includes a table of coefficients and error analysis.

Derivative order 7, x = 1, -1 + 31, -1 + 31 - 2 + 31, etc. Includes a table of coefficients and error analysis.

Error order: 33, Error: 2.440912514269835094 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 2.44092434350354482 × 10⁻⁹⁹
Error order: 33, Error: 2.44092434350354482 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 2.44092435334697828 × 10⁻⁹⁹
Error order: 34, Error: 2.44092435334697828 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 2.44092435334697828 × 10⁻⁹⁹
Error order: 34, Error: 2.44092435334697828 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 2.44092435334697828 × 10⁻⁹⁹

Derivative Order: 3 - x1 = 1 - x

Table with 3 rows and 11 columns of coefficients for the 3rd derivative.

Large numerical table with approximately 20 columns and 15 rows of data.

Quadrat 2

Error order: 33, Error: 8.33667849015930666 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 8.4245398798749123034 × 10⁻⁹⁹
Error order: 33, Error: 8.4245398798749123034 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 8.4244006705991174079 × 10⁻⁹⁹
Error order: 33, Error: 8.4244006705991174079 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 8.4244007113899404659 × 10⁻⁹⁹
Error order: 33, Error: 8.4244007113899404659 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 8.4244007113899404659 × 10⁻⁹⁹

Derivative Order: 4 - x1 = 1 - x

Table with 3 rows and 11 columns of coefficients for the 4th derivative.

Large numerical table with approximately 20 columns and 15 rows of data.

Quadrat 2

Error order: 32, Error: 5.003702403713147065 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 5.0279666208133080872 × 10⁻⁹⁹
Error order: 32, Error: 5.0279666208133080872 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 5.0279909438092846408 × 10⁻⁹⁹
Error order: 32, Error: 5.0279909438092846408 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 5.0279909481323395079 × 10⁻⁹⁹
Error order: 32, Error: 5.0279909481323395079 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 5.0279909481323395079 × 10⁻⁹⁹

Derivative Order: 5 - x1 = 1 - x

Table with 3 rows and 11 columns of coefficients for the 5th derivative.

Large numerical table with approximately 20 columns and 15 rows of data.

Quadrat 2

Error order: 31, Error: 2.73865718681608439 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 2.738670873084499749 × 10⁻⁹⁹
Error order: 31, Error: 2.738670873084499749 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 2.738670873084499749 × 10⁻⁹⁹
Error order: 31, Error: 2.738670873084499749 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 2.738670873084499749 × 10⁻⁹⁹
Error order: 31, Error: 2.738670873084499749 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 2.738670873084499749 × 10⁻⁹⁹

Derivative Order: 6 - x1 = 1 - x

Table with 3 rows and 11 columns of coefficients for the 6th derivative.

Large numerical table with approximately 20 columns and 15 rows of data.

Quadrat 2

Error order: 31, Error: 1.383664561716526434 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 1.390367461681934869 × 10⁻⁹⁹
Error order: 31, Error: 1.390367461681934869 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 1.390367461681934869 × 10⁻⁹⁹
Error order: 31, Error: 1.390367461681934869 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 1.390367461681934869 × 10⁻⁹⁹
Error order: 31, Error: 1.390367461681934869 × 10⁻⁹⁹, New Error: 1.390367461681934869 × 10⁻⁹⁹

Derivative Order: 7 - x1 = 1 - x

Table with 3 rows and 11 columns of coefficients for the 7th derivative.

Large numerical table with approximately 20 columns and 15 rows of data.

u(x) = ... (118107317973222720 + 36525633784928900) ...

u(x) = ... (244194776193988605707216000 + 377225155854791338291584000) ...

u(x) = ... (6821705252399014u_{-x+4} + 260785195823959040 + 279033864501938240) ...

Table with 11 columns of coefficients and 2 rows of values for u(x) and u'(x).

u(x) = ... (6821705252399014u_{-x+4} + 260785195823959040 + 279033864501938240) ...

Table with 11 columns of coefficients and 2 rows of values for u(x) and u'(x).

u(x) = ... (1042801020372080000x^{13} + (-3074544742159592850 + 3074544742159592850)) ...

u(x) = ... (1042801020372080000x^{13} + (-3074544742159592850 + 3074544742159592850)) ...

u(x) = ... (1042801020372080000x^{13} + (-3074544742159592850 + 3074544742159592850)) ...

u(x) = ... (1042801020372080000x^{13} + (-3074544742159592850 + 3074544742159592850)) ...

--- Derivative Order: 2, x1 = 1 ---

-7 +7 -7 -6 +7 -5 +7 -4 +7 -3 +7 -2 +7 -1 +7 1
-7 -6 -6 +6 -5 +6 -4 +6 -3 +6 -2 +6 -1 +6 6
-7 -5 -6 +5 -5 +5 -4 +5 -3 +5 -2 +5 -1 +5 5
-7 -4 -6 +4 -5 +4 -4 +4 -3 +4 -2 +4 -1 +4 4
-7 -3 -6 +3 -5 +3 -4 +3 -3 +3 -2 +3 -1 +3 3
-7 -2 -6 +2 -5 +2 -4 +2 -3 +2 -2 +2 -1 +2 2
-7 -1 -6 +1 -5 +1 -4 +1 -3 +1 -2 +1 -1 +1 1
-7 -6 -6 -5 -4 -3 -2 -1 0 1

Table with 10 columns of numerical data, likely representing coefficients or values for a polynomial expansion.

Equation for d^2/dx^2 u(x) with a long list of terms and coefficients, including terms like 1/(32709413708603490000) and various numerical values.

--- Derivative Order: 3, x1 = 1 ---

-7 +7 -7 -6 +7 -5 +7 -4 +7 -3 +7 -2 +7 -1 +7 1
-7 -6 -6 +6 -5 +6 -4 +6 -3 +6 -2 +6 -1 +6 6
-7 -5 -6 +5 -5 +5 -4 +5 -3 +5 -2 +5 -1 +5 5
-7 -4 -6 +4 -5 +4 -4 +4 -3 +4 -2 +4 -1 +4 4
-7 -3 -6 +3 -5 +3 -4 +3 -3 +3 -2 +3 -1 +3 3
-7 -2 -6 +2 -5 +2 -4 +2 -3 +2 -2 +2 -1 +2 2
-7 -1 -6 +1 -5 +1 -4 +1 -3 +1 -2 +1 -1 +1 1
-7 -6 -6 -5 -4 -3 -2 -1 0 1

Table with 10 columns of numerical data, similar to the first table, representing coefficients or values.

--- Derivative Order: 4, x1 = 1 ---

-7 +7 -7 -6 +7 -5 +7 -4 +7 -3 +7 -2 +7 -1 +7 1
-7 -6 -6 +6 -5 +6 -4 +6 -3 +6 -2 +6 -1 +6 6
-7 -5 -6 +5 -5 +5 -4 +5 -3 +5 -2 +5 -1 +5 5
-7 -4 -6 +4 -5 +4 -4 +4 -3 +4 -2 +4 -1 +4 4
-7 -3 -6 +3 -5 +3 -4 +3 -3 +3 -2 +3 -1 +3 3
-7 -2 -6 +2 -5 +2 -4 +2 -3 +2 -2 +2 -1 +2 2
-7 -1 -6 +1 -5 +1 -4 +1 -3 +1 -2 +1 -1 +1 1
-7 -6 -6 -5 -4 -3 -2 -1 0 1

Table with 10 columns of numerical data, similar to the previous tables, representing coefficients or values.

--- Derivative Order: 5, x1 = 1 ---

-7 +7 -7 -6 +7 -5 +7 -4 +7 -3 +7 -2 +7 -1 +7 1
-7 -6 -6 +6 -5 +6 -4 +6 -3 +6 -2 +6 -1 +6 6
-7 -5 -6 +5 -5 +5 -4 +5 -3 +5 -2 +5 -1 +5 5
-7 -4 -6 +4 -5 +4 -4 +4 -3 +4 -2 +4 -1 +4 4
-7 -3 -6 +3 -5 +3 -4 +3 -3 +3 -2 +3 -1 +3 3
-7 -2 -6 +2 -5 +2 -4 +2 -3 +2 -2 +2 -1 +2 2
-7 -1 -6 +1 -5 +1 -4 +1 -3 +1 -2 +1 -1 +1 1
-7 -6 -6 -5 -4 -3 -2 -1 0 1

Table with 10 columns of numerical data, similar to the previous tables, representing coefficients or values.

--- Derivative Order: 6, x1 = 1 ---

-8 +8 -7 +8 -6 +8 -5 +8 -4 +8 -3 +8 -2 +8 -1 +8 1
-8 -7 -7 +7 -6 +7 -5 +7 -4 +7 -3 +7 -2 +7 -1 +7 7
-8 -6 -7 +6 -5 +6 -4 +6 -3 +6 -2 +6 -1 +6 6
-8 -5 -7 +5 -4 +5 -3 +5 -2 +5 -1 +5 5
-8 -4 -7 +4 -3 +4 -2 +4 -1 +4 4
-8 -3 -7 +3 -2 +3 -1 +3 3
-8 -2 -7 +2 -1 +2 2
-8 -1 -7 +1 1 1
-8 -7 -7 -6 -5 -4 -3 -2 -1 0 1

Table with 10 columns of numerical data, similar to the previous tables, representing coefficients or values.

--- Derivative Order: 7, x1 = 1 ---

-8 +8 -7 +8 -6 +8 -5 +8 -4 +8 -3 +8 -2 +8 -1 +8 1
-8 -7 -7 +7 -6 +7 -5 +7 -4 +7 -3 +7 -2 +7 -1 +7 7
-8 -6 -7 +6 -5 +6 -4 +6 -3 +6 -2 +6 -1 +6 6
-8 -5 -7 +5 -4 +5 -3 +5 -2 +5 -1 +5 5
-8 -4 -7 +4 -3 +4 -2 +4 -1 +4 4
-8 -3 -7 +3 -2 +3 -1 +3 3
-8 -2 -7 +2 -1 +2 2
-8 -1 -7 +1 1 1
-8 -7 -7 -6 -5 -4 -3 -2 -1 0 1

Table with 10 columns of numerical data, similar to the previous tables, representing coefficients or values.

10^100 u(x) = ... (10290 + 10290) 1/256 (256 u_{-1} - (6144 + 6144) u_{-2} + ...)

Error order: 3. Error: 1.83086169073619715 x 10^-17. New Error: 1.8322257808036552 x 10^-17

10^100 u(x) = ... (512 u_{-1} + (13056 - 13056) u_{-2} - 31344 u_{-3} + ...)

Error order: 3. Error: 2.06670151067360998 x 10^-17. New Error: 2.0683957319325926 x 10^-17

10^100 u(x) = ... (-512 u_{-1} + (1284 + 1284) u_{-2} - 35252 u_{-3} + ...)

Error order: 3. Error: 1.8564870711629323 x 10^-17. New Error: 1.8564870711629323 x 10^-17

10^100 u(x) = ... (-1024 u_{-1} + (-29184 + 29184) u_{-2} + 781980 u_{-3} - (6697728 + 6697728) u_{-4} + ...)

Error order: 3. Error: 2.3024668811608970 x 10^-17. New Error: 2.3024668811608970 x 10^-17

10^100 u(x) = ... (1024 u_{-1} + (-30720 + 30720) u_{-2} + 875200 u_{-3} + (787980 - 787980) u_{-4} - 100465200 u_{-5} + ...)

Error order: 3. Error: 2.4188136211862958 x 10^-17. New Error: 2.4188136211862958 x 10^-17

D^2 u(x) = ... (8 + 6) u_{-1} + (8 - 24) u_{-2} + (-16 + (-4 + 12)) u_{-3} + ...)

Error order: 2. Error: 2.66302251505166571 x 10^-16. New Error: 2.664802879286579931 x 10^-16

10^100 u(x) = ... (8 + 6) u_{-1} + (8 - 24) u_{-2} + (-16 + (-4 + 12)) u_{-3} + ...)

Error order: 2. Error: 3.3083123068305454712 x 10^-12. New Error: 3.3083123068305454712 x 10^-12

$\frac{d^4}{dx^4} u(x) = \frac{1}{160000000000} (622000 u_{-2} + 4000000 u_{-1} + 1148500000 - 2850000) u_{0-1} + \dots$

$\frac{d^4}{dx^4} u(x) = \frac{1}{320000000000} (6520000 u_{-2} + 45000000 u_{-1} + 1472625000 - 20250000) u_{0-1} + \dots$

$\frac{d^4}{dx^4} u(x) = \frac{1}{320000000000} (31250000 u_{-2} + 25000000 u_{-1} + 91781250000 - 1781250000) u_{0-1} + \dots$

$\frac{d^4}{dx^4} u(x) = \frac{1}{200 \cdot 16!} (520 + 2679) u_{-2-1} + \dots$

$\frac{d^4}{dx^4} u(x) = \frac{1}{200 \cdot 16!} (520 + 2679) u_{-2-1} + \dots$

Mathematical expressions involving various constants and variables, including terms like u_{i-1} , u_{i-2} , and u_{i-3} . Includes a table with numerical values and a section labeled "Quadrant 3".

Table with numerical values and a derivative order label.

Table with 3 columns and 3 rows of numerical values.

Table with 3 columns and 3 rows of numerical values.

Table with 3 columns and 3 rows of numerical values.

Quadrant 3 section with mathematical expressions and error values.

Quadrant 3 section with mathematical expressions and error values.

Quadrant 3 section with mathematical expressions and error values.

Quadrant 3 section with mathematical expressions and error values.

Quadrant 3 section with mathematical expressions and error values.

Quadrant 3 section with mathematical expressions and error values.

Quadrant 3 section with mathematical expressions and error values.

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Quadrant 3 section with mathematical expressions and error values.

Quadrant 3 section with mathematical expressions and error values.

u(x) = 1/14240000 * (11878709900800064184 - 15522592828138836801 * u_{x-1} + ...)

u(x) = 1/16900 * (285001462576 + 593867069120 * u_{x-1} + ...)

u(x) = 1/16900 * (285001462576 + 593867069120 * u_{x-1} + ...)

u(x) = 1/16900 * (285001462576 + 593867069120 * u_{x-1} + ...)

u(x) = 1/16900 * (285001462576 + 593867069120 * u_{x-1} + ...)

u(x) = 1/16900 * (285001462576 + 593867069120 * u_{x-1} + ...)

u(x) = 1/16900 * (285001462576 + 593867069120 * u_{x-1} + ...)

u(x) = 1/16900 * (285001462576 + 593867069120 * u_{x-1} + ...)

u(x) = 1/16900 * (285001462576 + 593867069120 * u_{x-1} + ...)

u(x) = 1/16900 * (285001462576 + 593867069120 * u_{x-1} + ...)

u(x) = 1/16900 * (285001462576 + 593867069120 * u_{x-1} + ...)

u(x) = 1/16900 * (285001462576 + 593867069120 * u_{x-1} + ...)

u(x) = 1/16900 * (285001462576 + 593867069120 * u_{x-1} + ...)

u(x) = 1/16900 * (285001462576 + 593867069120 * u_{x-1} + ...)

138266860592640) u_{n-2} + (33973790428040 + 364285999120) u_{n-1} + (178860614663420 + 83792014698120) u_n + ...

Q(x, x^2), Quadant 3

Error order, Error, 3.06275902128741810 x 10^-10, New Error, 3.07505238518546345 x 10^-10

u^{(4)}(x) = 1 / (296590000 * 4x^4) [343 (-13369046961069088000 + 146209674232673216000) u_{n-2} + ...]

Error order, Error, 7.4964947635754222 x 10^-10, New Error, 8.7327197299405193 x 10^-10

Q(x^2), Quadant 3

Table with 4 columns and 4 rows of numerical values, representing a 2D grid of data points.

u^{(4)}(x) = 126 (-25465 + 52377) u_{n-2} + (1014560 + 236504) u_{n-1} + (423487 - 1237345) u_n + ...

Error order, Error, 6.5374451086010758 x 10^-10, New Error, 6.5487663746131484 x 10^-10

u^{(4)}(x) = 1 / (422 * 4x^4) [31752 (-104744952 + 1333780305) u_{n-2} + ...]

Error order, Error, 6.5374451086010758 x 10^-10, New Error, 6.5487663746131484 x 10^-10

u^{(6)}(x) = 1 / (4225 * 6x^6) [31752 (-104744952 + 1333780305) u_{n-2} + ...]

Error order, Error, 4.9842186139094662 x 10^-10, New Error, 4.51680694173496234 x 10^-10

Q(x^2, x^3), Quadant 3

Table with 4 columns and 4 rows of numerical values, representing a 2D grid of data points.

Error order, Error, 4.51680694173496234 x 10^-10, New Error, 4.51680694173496234 x 10^-10

u^{(6)}(x) = 1 / (4225 * 6x^6) [28578 (-157199832 + 1568211005) u_{n-2} + ...]

Error order, Error, 2.55337907419121385 x 10^-10, New Error, 2.5662449796940991 x 10^-10

u^{(8)}(x) = 1 / (4225 * 8x^8) [28578 (-157199832 + 1568211005) u_{n-2} + ...]

Error order, Error, 2.5662449796940991 x 10^-10, New Error, 2.5662449796940991 x 10^-10

u^{(10)}(x) = 1 / (4225 * 10x^10) [28578 (-157199832 + 1568211005) u_{n-2} + ...]

Error order, Error, 2.5662449796940991 x 10^-10, New Error, 2.5662449796940991 x 10^-10

u^{(12)}(x) = 1 / (4225 * 12x^12) [28578 (-157199832 + 1568211005) u_{n-2} + ...]

Error order, Error, 2.5662449796940991 x 10^-10, New Error, 2.5662449796940991 x 10^-10

Q(x^2, x^3, x^4), Quadant 3

Derivative Order 10... Matrix of coefficients

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of numerical coefficients for Derivative Order 10

u(x) = 252 ((55055 + 18937) u_{i-1} + ... + (-55055 + 18937) u_{i+1}), Q(Δx^10), Quadram 3

Error order... New Error... for Derivative Order 10

u(x) = 1 / (169 Δx^10) [127008 ((1336221528 + 1042576535) u_{i-10} + ... + (-94542916 + 3210521212) u_{i+10})], Q(Δx^10), Quadram 3

u(x, k2) = 1 / (169 Δx^10) [127008 ((1336221528 + 1042576535) u_{i-10-2} + ... + (-1077624252 + 11187377250) u_{i+10+2})], Q(Δx^10), Quadram 3

u(x, k2) = 1 / (169 Δx^10) [127008 ((1336221528 + 1042576535) u_{i-10-4} + ... + (-113039505528 + 134138902168) u_{i+10+4})], Q(Δx^10), Quadram 3

Error order... New Error... for Derivative Order 10 (k2)

Derivative Order 11... Matrix of coefficients

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of numerical coefficients for Derivative Order 11

u(x) = 924 ((165958 - 94685) u_{i-1} + ... + (-94685 + 165958) u_{i+1}), Q(Δx^11), Quadram 3

Error order... New Error... for Derivative Order 11

Derivative Order 12... Matrix of coefficients

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of numerical coefficients for Derivative Order 12

u(x) = 99792 ((135 - 663) u_{i-3} + ... + (-663 + 135) u_{i+3}), Q(Δx^12), Quadram 3

Error order... New Error... for Derivative Order 12

Derivative Order 13... Matrix of coefficients

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of numerical coefficients for Derivative Order 13

u(x) = - (4490640 + 5887728) u_{i-3} + ... + (5887728 - 4490640) u_{i+3}, Q(Δx^13), Quadram 3

Error order... New Error... for Derivative Order 13

Derivative Order 14... Matrix of coefficients

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of numerical coefficients for Derivative Order 14

u(x) = - (6985440 + 465961) u_{i-3} + ... + (465961 - 6985440) u_{i+3}, Q(Δx^14), Quadram 3

Error order... New Error... for Derivative Order 14

Derivative Order 15... Matrix of coefficients

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of numerical coefficients for Derivative Order 15

u(x) = - (490640 + 5887728) u_{i-3} + ... + (5887728 - 490640) u_{i+3}, Q(Δx^15), Quadram 3

Error order... New Error... for Derivative Order 15

$$\frac{d^{13}}{dx^{13}} u(x) = \frac{1}{125 \cdot 3!^{13}} (693 \{ (-707860582 + 254795190) u_{i-4} + (32859520991 - 29592451031) u_{i-3} + (-162693198720 + 89112950550) u_{i-2} + (59438670759 - 18469446047) u_{i-1} + (-1045535000 + 1045535000) u_i + (35296982617 - 5611492991) u_{i+1} + (371448338190 - 231475766880) u_{i+2} + (17903492479080 - 13817421941310) u_{i+3} + (4101057408760 - 4101057408760) u_{i+4} + (-18469446047 - 59438670759) u_{i+5} + (-97807573890 + 66432885480) u_{i+6} + (-13965641880690 - 11320469877960) u_{i+7} + (-695118516480 + 695118516480) u_{i+8} + (13817421941310 - 17903492479080) u_{i+9} + (-89112950550 + 162693198720) u_{i+10} + (16990210305 - 26190093865) u_{i+11} + (2569459298120 - 2569459298120) u_{i+12} + (11320469877960 - 13965641880690) u_{i+13} + (2314757868280 - 3714483381960) u_{i+14} + (29592451031 - 32859520991) u_{i+15} + (-396388876 + 396388876) u_{i+16} + (26190093865 - 16909210305) u_{i+17} + (-66432885480 + 97807573890) u_{i+18} + (5611492991 - 35296982617) u_{i+19} \}, \text{Quadram } J$$

... Derivative Order: 14 - x!-1 ...

-4	-3	-2	-1	0
-4 -1	-3 -1	-2 -1	-1 -1	-1
-4 -2	-3 -2	-2 -2	-1 -2	-2
-4 -3	-3 -3	-2 -3	-1 -3	-3
-4 -4	-3 -4	-2 -4	-1 -4	-4

$$\frac{d^{14}}{dx^{14}} u(x) = \frac{1}{125 \cdot 3!^{14}} (4851 \{ (-168837209 + 395369905) u_{i-4} + (398399338 - 24881192646) u_{i-3} + (-25503101280 + 99083349450) u_{i-2} + (14951138482 - 29975347906) u_{i-1} + 774038000 u_i + (11602753238 - 16823501814) u_{i+1} + (509345704480 - 2418416922640) u_{i+2} + (1442055513260 - 12498301615320) u_{i+3} - 3173305982480 u_{i+4} - (14951138482 + 29975347906) u_{i+5} + (-11802807540 + 66783111030) u_{i+6} + (975186432900 - 10166275569960) u_{i+7} + 55262265383520 u_{i+8} - (1442055513260 + 12498301615320) u_{i+9} + (25503101280 + 99083349450) u_{i+10} - (4216383970 + 17199785990) u_{i+11} - 2078834067920 u_{i+12} - (975186432900 + 10166275569960) u_{i+13} - (509345704480 + 2418416922640) u_{i+14} - (398399338 + 24881192646) u_{i+15} + 3245730621 u_{i+16} + (4216383970 - 17199785990) u_{i+17} + (1180280740 + 66783111030) u_{i+18} - (11602753238 + 16823501814) u_{i+19} + (168837209 + 395369905) u_{i+20} \}, \text{Quadram } J$$

... Derivative Order: 15 - x!-1 ...

-4	-3	-2	-1	0
-4 -1	-3 -1	-2 -1	-1 -1	-1
-4 -2	-3 -2	-2 -2	-1 -2	-2
-4 -3	-3 -3	-2 -3	-1 -3	-3
-4 -4	-3 -4	-2 -4	-1 -4	-4

$$\frac{d^{15}}{dx^{15}} u(x) = \frac{1}{100 \cdot 3!^{15}} (14553 \{ (168837209 + 378933895) u_{i-4} + (-17049880184 + 16380519672) u_{i-3} + (51006202560 + 80582669100) u_{i-2} - (10249110728 + 28764937976) u_{i-1} + (487257735 + 487257735) u_i - (4046741256 + 1933195272) u_{i+1} - (1328733145120 + 1948816617440) u_{i+2} - (17472609948160 + 917700584280) u_{i+3} - (2077813379040 - 2077813379040) u_{i+4} - (28764937976 + 10249110728) u_{i+5} + (38478875220 + 53352153560) u_{i+6} - (630891448240 + 7512514306560) u_{i+7} + (3714351008480 + 3714351008480) u_{i+8} - (9177005843280 + 7472609948160) u_{i+9} + (80582669100 + 51006202560) u_{i+10} - (14814447880 + 8855961400) u_{i+11} - (1422252402720 + 1422252402720) u_{i+12} - (145531430660 + 630891448240) u_{i+13} - (1948816617440 + 1328733145120) u_{i+14} - (16380519672 + 17049880184) u_{i+15} + (224865369 + 224865369) u_{i+16} - (8855961400 + 14814447880) u_{i+17} + (53352153560 + 38478875220) u_{i+18} - (1933195272 + 4046741256) u_{i+19} + (378933895 + 168837209) u_{i+20} \}, \text{Quadram } J$$

... Derivative Order: 16 - x!-1 ...

-4	-3	-2	-1	0
-4 -1	-3 -1	-2 -1	-1 -1	-1
-4 -2	-3 -2	-2 -2	-1 -2	-2
-4 -3	-3 -3	-2 -3	-1 -3	-3
-4 -4	-3 -4	-2 -4	-1 -4	-4

$$\frac{d^{16}}{dx^{16}} u(x) = \frac{1}{25 \cdot 3!^{16}} (29106 \{ (159210263 + 54161920) u_{i-4} + (-9423209904 + 525514768) u_{i-3} + (36700189740 + 7123723200) u_{i-2} - (10686273584 + 4839114128) u_{i-1} + 259131415 u_i - (6827661744 + 4219634448) u_{i+1} - (933542452160 + 156729489920) u_{i+2} - (4664792927520 + 418667045760) u_{i+3} - 1145737398720 u_{i+4} + (-10686273584 + 4839114128) u_{i+5} + (26561858220 + 3896195960) u_{i+6} - (395237508640 + 30887858400) u_{i+7} + 2106618996640 u_{i+8} + (-4664792927520 + 418667045760) u_{i+9} + (36700189740 - 7123723200) u_{i+10} + (-685523760 + 1773195760) u_{i+11} - 81895317120 u_{i+12} + (-395237508640 + 30887858400) u_{i+13} + (-933542452160 + 156729489920) u_{i+14} - (9423209904 + 525514768) u_{i+15} + 131196183 u_{i+16} - (685523760 + 1773195760) u_{i+17} + (26561858220 - 3896195960) u_{i+18} + (-6827661744 + 4219634448) u_{i+19} + (159210263 - 54161920) u_{i+20} \}, \text{Quadram } J$$

... Derivative Order: 17 - x!-1 ...

-4	-3	-2	-1	0
-4 -1	-3 -1	-2 -1	-1 -1	-1
-4 -2	-3 -2	-2 -2	-1 -2	-2
-4 -3	-3 -3	-2 -3	-1 -3	-3
-4 -4	-3 -4	-2 -4	-1 -4	-4

$$\frac{d^{17}}{dx^{17}} u(x) = \frac{1}{25 \cdot 3!^{17}} (931392 \{ (13270778 - 7193380) u_{i-4} + (-5339236607 + 641145769) u_{i-3} + (2641232880 - 1892238975) u_{i-2} + (-930780241 + 368162353) u_{i-1} + (15339175 - 15339175) u_i + (-699032903 + 184524169) u_{i+1} + (-6757354340 + 50273298620) u_{i+2} + (-312249750120 + 26733309090) u_{i+3} - (70108399140 + 70108398140) u_{i+4} + (-368162353 + 930780241) u_{i+5} + (1926795295 - 148081620) u_{i+6} + (-267919299310 + 233310048840) u_{i+7} - (1317308989520 - 1317308989520) u_{i+8} + (-26733309090 + 312249750120) u_{i+9} + (1892238975 - 2641232880) u_{i+10} + (-332398095 + 557624735) u_{i+11} - (52303490980 + 52303490980) u_{i+12} + (-233310048840 + 267919299310) u_{i+13} + (-50273298620 + 67557354340) u_{i+14} - (641145769 + 5339236607) u_{i+15} + (8495699 - 8495699) u_{i+16} + (-557624735 + 332398095) u_{i+17} + (1480816620 - 1926705285) u_{i+18} + (-184524169 + 699032903) u_{i+19} + (7193380 - 13270778) u_{i+20} \}, \text{Quadram } J$$

... Derivative Order: 18 - x!-1 ...

-4	-3	-2	-1	0
-4 -1	-3 -1	-2 -1	-1 -1	-1
-4 -2	-3 -2	-2 -2	-1 -2	-2
-4 -3	-3 -3	-2 -3	-1 -3	-3
-4 -4	-3 -4	-2 -4	-1 -4	-4

$$\frac{d^{18}}{dx^{18}} u(x) = \frac{1}{25 \cdot 3!^{18}} (4191264 \{ (2068397 - 8145795) u_{i-4} + (57426676 + 454081908) u_{i-3} + (239637240 - 1737625050) u_{i-2} + (-203755836 + 490764988) u_{i-1} - 31207501 u_i + (-193968884 + 354821652) u_{i+1} + (-5796583840 + 46161279120) u_{i+2} + (-14669450280 + 223674114960) u_{i+3} + 5334855440 u_{i+4} + (203755836 + 490764988) u_{i+5} + (155383020 - 1379706390) u_{i+6} + (-11804715000 + 197460416880) u_{i+7} - 102653809960 u_{i+8} + (14669450280 + 223674114960) u_{i+9} - (239637240 + 1737625050) u_{i+10} + (96324060 + 351839420) u_{i+11} + 41522161360 u_{i+12} + (11804715000 + 197460416880) u_{i+13} + (5796583840 + 46161279120) u_{i+14} + (-57426676 + 454081908) u_{i+15} - 6843476 u_{i+16} + (-96324060 + 351839420) u_{i+17} - (155383020 + 1379706390) u_{i+18} + (193968884 + 354821652) u_{i+19} - (2068397 + 8145795) u_{i+20} \}, \text{Quadram } J$$

... Derivative Order: 19 - x!-1 ...

-4	-3	-2	-1	0
-4 -1	-3 -1	-2 -1	-1 -1	-1
-4 -2	-3 -2	-2 -2	-1 -2	-2
-4 -3	-3 -3	-2 -3	-1 -3	-3
-4 -4	-3 -4	-2 -4	-1 -4	-4

u(x) = 1 / (2468057832000 dx^11) [2079 (-11276771000260194500 - 18934728639179656600) u_{x-1} + ... + 33969505618589921234] ...

Error order: 24, Error: 7.6750543302989847915 x 10^-10, New Error: 7.711897064403274732 x 10^-10
Error order: 24, Error: 7.711897064403274732 x 10^-10, New Error: 7.711897064403274732 x 10^-10
Error order: 24, Error: 7.7119340244372044043 x 10^-98, New Error: 7.7119340244372044043 x 10^-98
Error order: 24, Error: 7.7119340244372044043 x 10^-98, New Error: 7.7119340244372044043 x 10^-98

--- Derivative Order: 13 - x! ---

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of numerical values.

u(x) = 1 / (37901205000 dx^11) [2079 (-51070842801048077800 + 23625439813483888810) u_{x-1} + ... + 334771906483040076539] ...

Error order: 23, Error: 2.7201177349219092621 x 10^-10, New Error: 2.7331521384231001038 x 10^-10
Error order: 23, Error: 2.7331521384231001038 x 10^-10, New Error: 2.7331521384231001038 x 10^-10
Error order: 23, Error: 2.7331652171031718556 x 10^-97, New Error: 2.7331652171031718556 x 10^-97
Error order: 23, Error: 2.7331652171031718556 x 10^-97, New Error: 2.7331652171031718556 x 10^-97

--- Derivative Order: 14 - x! ---

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of numerical values.

u(x) = 1 / (189050625000 dx^11) [4553 (-9612758849818010395 + 590087473306088193) u_{x-1} + ... + 1830627629309868363396] ...

Error order: 22, Error: 9.178323452220773528 x 10^-10, New Error: 9.222202007895615086 x 10^-10
Error order: 22, Error: 9.222202007895615086 x 10^-10, New Error: 9.222202007895615086 x 10^-10
Error order: 22, Error: 9.222241643867791 x 10^-97, New Error: 9.222241643867791 x 10^-97
Error order: 22, Error: 9.222241643867791 x 10^-97, New Error: 9.222241643867791 x 10^-97

--- Derivative Order: 15 - x! ---

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of numerical values.

u(x) = 1 / (4936115660000 dx^11) [4369 (-586652248631656740518 + 153663281325928503018) u_{x-1} + ... + 22335365000] ...

Error order: 21, Error: 2.95967551628244304 x 10^-10, New Error: 2.95967551628244304 x 10^-10
Error order: 21, Error: 2.95967551628244304 x 10^-10, New Error: 2.95967551628244304 x 10^-10
Error order: 21, Error: 2.9596896214733847055 x 10^-10, New Error: 2.9596896214733847055 x 10^-10
Error order: 21, Error: 2.9596896214733847055 x 10^-10, New Error: 2.9596896214733847055 x 10^-10

--- Derivative Order: 16 - x! ---

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of numerical values.

u(x) = 1 / (14517987250 dx^11) [4369 (-5086284728783776150 + 916173160325161150) u_{x-1} + ... + 14517987250] ...

Error order: 20, Error: 8.9796109228834154295 x 10^-10, New Error: 9.02238186874703387 x 10^-10
Error order: 20, Error: 9.02238186874703387 x 10^-10, New Error: 9.02241048756437966 x 10^-10
Error order: 20, Error: 9.02241048756437966 x 10^-10, New Error: 9.02241048756437966 x 10^-10
Error order: 20, Error: 9.02241048756437966 x 10^-10, New Error: 9.02241048756437966 x 10^-10

--- Derivative Order: 17 - x! ---

Table with 5 columns and 5 rows of numerical values.

u(x) = 1 / (14517987250 dx^11) [4369 (-5086284728783776150 + 916173160325161150) u_{x-1} + ... + 14517987250] ...

Error order: 20, Error: 8.9796109228834154295 x 10^-10, New Error: 9.02238186874703387 x 10^-10
Error order: 20, Error: 9.02238186874703387 x 10^-10, New Error: 9.02241048756437966 x 10^-10
Error order: 20, Error: 9.02241048756437966 x 10^-10, New Error: 9.02241048756437966 x 10^-10
Error order: 20, Error: 9.02241048756437966 x 10^-10, New Error: 9.02241048756437966 x 10^-10

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{(4x)^2} \left(-1314314390954528034985950 + 57821675866425287349750 \right) u_{0,-4} + \dots$$

Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.736023915408189649 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.7462122926151200530 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.7462122926151200530 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.746225210896848935128 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.746225210896848935128 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.746225210896848935128 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.746225210896848935128 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.746225210896848935128 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.746225210896848935128 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.746225210896848935128 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{(4x)^4} \left(-533963361405177463023647960 + 5967899055758262671828960 \right) u_{0,-4} + \dots$$

Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.06993632693308780 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{(4x)^7} \left(533963361405177463023647960 + 79192504139593940100490240000 \right) u_{0,-4} + \dots$$

Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.076212771051818661 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{(4x)^8} \left(71250846083327252463238474525 + 214581176304268724275906603225 \right) u_{0,-4} + \dots$$

Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{(4x)^9} \left(71250846083327252463238474525 + 214581176304268724275906603225 \right) u_{0,-4} + \dots$$

Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order, 4*r*, *Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰, *New Error*, 1.35224849506987730191 × 10⁻¹⁰⁰

--- Derivative Order: 2 - x1 -1 ---

Table with 10 columns and 10 rows of numerical values, representing the derivative order 2 for x1 -1.

Large table with multiple columns and rows of numerical values, representing the main data for the derivative order 2.

u(x) = 1 / (3287941397086034970000...), Error order: 60, New Error: 1.91769647570760277 x 10^-90, Error order: 60, New Error: 1.91769647570760277 x 10^-90, Error order: 60, New Error: 1.91769647570760277 x 10^-90, Error order: 60, New Error: 1.91769647570760277 x 10^-90.

--- Derivative Order: 3 - x1 -1 ---

Table with 10 columns and 10 rows of numerical values, representing the derivative order 3 for x1 -1.

Large table with multiple columns and rows of numerical values, representing the main data for the derivative order 3.

u(x) = 1 / (10912698944428322757410000...), Error order: 61, New Error: 2.984234909133086 x 10^-91, Error order: 61, New Error: 2.984234909133086 x 10^-91, Error order: 61, New Error: 2.984234909133086 x 10^-91, Error order: 61, New Error: 2.984234909133086 x 10^-91.

--- Derivative Order: 4 - x1 -1 ---

Table with 10 columns and 10 rows of numerical values, representing the derivative order 4 for x1 -1.

Large table with multiple columns and rows of numerical values, representing the main data for the derivative order 4.

u(x) = 1 / (21714043779022813850000...), Error order: 60, New Error: 1.91769647570760277 x 10^-90, Error order: 60, New Error: 1.91769647570760277 x 10^-90, Error order: 60, New Error: 1.91769647570760277 x 10^-90, Error order: 60, New Error: 1.91769647570760277 x 10^-90.

--- Derivative Order: 1 - x1 -1 ---

Table with 10 columns and 10 rows of numerical values, representing the derivative order 1 for x1 -1.

Error order: 60, New Error: 1.904497554238069195 x 10^-90, Error order: 60, New Error: 1.91769647570760277 x 10^-90.

$u(x) = \frac{1}{512 \Delta x^4} (4306471 u_{1,1} - 22952512 + 22982512) u_{2,1} + \dots$

Order Δx^4 terms

$u(x) = \frac{1}{512 \Delta x^4} (-129140163 + 129140163) u_{1,1} + \dots$

Order Δx^4 terms

$u(x) = \frac{1}{512 \Delta x^4} (387402848 u_{1,1} + 232452234 - 232452234) u_{2,1} + \dots$

Order Δx^4 terms

$u(x) = \frac{1}{512 \Delta x^4} (387402848 u_{1,1} + 232452234 - 232452234) u_{2,1} + \dots$

Order Δx^4 terms

$u(x) = \frac{1}{512 \Delta x^4} (116261467 - 116261467) u_{1,1} + \dots$

Order Δx^4 terms

$u(x) = \frac{1}{512 \Delta x^4} (116261467 - 116261467) u_{1,1} + \dots$

Order Δx^4 terms

$u(x) = \frac{1}{512 \Delta x^4} (116261467 - 116261467) u_{1,1} + \dots$

Order Δx^4 terms

Mathematical expressions for the first quadrant of a grid, showing coordinates and values for various points. Includes a small table for the first quadrant.

Mathematical expressions for the second quadrant of a grid, showing coordinates and values for various points. Includes a small table for the second quadrant.

Mathematical expressions for the third quadrant of a grid, showing coordinates and values for various points. Includes a small table for the third quadrant.

Mathematical expressions for the fourth quadrant of a grid, showing coordinates and values for various points. Includes a small table for the fourth quadrant.

Mathematical expressions for the fifth quadrant of a grid, showing coordinates and values for various points. Includes a small table for the fifth quadrant.

Mathematical expressions for the sixth quadrant of a grid, showing coordinates and values for various points. Includes a small table for the sixth quadrant.

Mathematical expressions for the seventh quadrant of a grid, showing coordinates and values for various points. Includes a small table for the seventh quadrant.

Mathematical expressions for the eighth quadrant of a grid, showing coordinates and values for various points. Includes a small table for the eighth quadrant.

Mathematical expressions for the ninth quadrant of a grid, showing coordinates and values for various points. Includes a small table for the ninth quadrant.

$$\frac{d^{24}}{dx^{24}} u(x) = \frac{1}{10000 \text{ rad}^{24}} [243 \dots + (-429670243646820 + 132303154202100) u_{n+1} + \dots + (-11496049349400) u_{n+24}]$$

$$\frac{d^{10}}{dx^{10}} u(x) = 127008 1u_n + (166520 + 801360) u_{n+1} + (585180 + 1368000) u_{n+2} + (289800 + 4374000) u_{n+3} + (36000 + 37800) u_{n+4} + (-166520 + 801360) u_{n+5} \dots$$

... Derivative Order: 5 - x! = 1 ...

$$\frac{d^5}{dx^5} u(x) = \frac{1}{dx^5} [(252 + 252) 1u_n + (960 + 630) u_{n+1} + (210 + 90) u_{n+2} + (630 + 900) u_{n+3} + (330 + 330) u_{n+4} + (642 + 456) u_{n+5} + (90 + 210) u_{n+6} + (456 + 642) u_{n+7} + (120 + 120) u_{n+8}]$$

$$\frac{d^{100}}{dx^{100}} u(x) = 127008 1u_n + (166520 + 801360) u_{n+1} + (585180 + 1368000) u_{n+2} + (289800 + 4374000) u_{n+3} + (36000 + 37800) u_{n+4} + (-166520 + 801360) u_{n+5} \dots$$

... Derivative Order: 6 - x! = 1 ...

$$\frac{d^6}{dx^6} u(x) = \frac{1}{dx^6} [(252 + 252) 1u_n + (960 + 630) u_{n+1} + (210 + 90) u_{n+2} + (630 + 900) u_{n+3} + (330 + 330) u_{n+4} + (642 + 456) u_{n+5} + (90 + 210) u_{n+6} + (456 + 642) u_{n+7} + (120 + 120) u_{n+8}]$$

$$\frac{d^{105}}{dx^{105}} u(x) = \frac{1}{dx^{105}} [(3200616 + 32006016) 1u_n + (-24005420 + 365703040) u_{n+1} + (-552076560 + 139145840) u_{n+2} + (-30951640 + 2041540200) u_{n+3} + (260200 + 959509000) u_{n+4} + (2223000 + 170940000) u_{n+5} + (415000 + 1178000) u_{n+6} + (-365703040 + 24005420) u_{n+7} + (-71331360 + 71331360) u_{n+8} + \dots]$$

$$\frac{d^{105}}{dx^{105}} u(x) = \frac{1}{dx^{105}} [(3200616 + 32006016) 1u_n + (-24005420 + 365703040) u_{n+1} + (-552076560 + 139145840) u_{n+2} + (-30951640 + 2041540200) u_{n+3} + (260200 + 959509000) u_{n+4} + (2223000 + 170940000) u_{n+5} + (415000 + 1178000) u_{n+6} + (-365703040 + 24005420) u_{n+7} + (-71331360 + 71331360) u_{n+8} + \dots]$$

$$\frac{d^{110}}{dx^{110}} u(x) = \frac{1}{dx^{110}} [(16131032064 u_n + (-205558261760 + 4227941120) u_{n+1} + (-96014080000 + 415209473280) u_{n+2} + (-209743369200 + 1464150038400) u_{n+3} + (-2125573684800 + 2211754560000) u_{n+4} + (-899865288000 + 1370968856000) u_{n+5} + (-168078240000 + 395734240000) u_{n+6} + (-12201840000 + 53401680000) u_{n+7} + (-132840000 + 272160000) u_{n+8} + \dots]$$

$$\frac{d^{110}}{dx^{110}} u(x) = \frac{1}{dx^{110}} [(16131032064 u_n + (-205558261760 + 4227941120) u_{n+1} + (-96014080000 + 415209473280) u_{n+2} + (-209743369200 + 1464150038400) u_{n+3} + (-2125573684800 + 2211754560000) u_{n+4} + (-899865288000 + 1370968856000) u_{n+5} + (-168078240000 + 395734240000) u_{n+6} + (-12201840000 + 53401680000) u_{n+7} + (-132840000 + 272160000) u_{n+8} + \dots]$$

$$\frac{d^{115}}{dx^{115}} u(x) = \frac{1}{dx^{115}} [(16131032064 u_n + (-205558261760 + 4227941120) u_{n+1} + (-96014080000 + 415209473280) u_{n+2} + (-209743369200 + 1464150038400) u_{n+3} + (-2125573684800 + 2211754560000) u_{n+4} + (-899865288000 + 1370968856000) u_{n+5} + (-168078240000 + 395734240000) u_{n+6} + (-12201840000 + 53401680000) u_{n+7} + (-132840000 + 272160000) u_{n+8} + \dots]$$

$$\frac{d^{115}}{dx^{115}} u(x) = \frac{1}{dx^{115}} [(16131032064 u_n + (-205558261760 + 4227941120) u_{n+1} + (-96014080000 + 415209473280) u_{n+2} + (-209743369200 + 1464150038400) u_{n+3} + (-2125573684800 + 2211754560000) u_{n+4} + (-899865288000 + 1370968856000) u_{n+5} + (-168078240000 + 395734240000) u_{n+6} + (-12201840000 + 53401680000) u_{n+7} + (-132840000 + 272160000) u_{n+8} + \dots]$$

... Derivative Order: 6 - x! = 1 ...

$$\frac{d^6}{dx^6} u(x) = \frac{1}{dx^6} [(-648 1u_n - 288 - 2288) u_{n+1} + (-126 + 486) u_{n+2} + (288 - 2288) u_{n+3} + (1080 1u_n - 216 - 1764) u_{n+4} + (126 - 486 1u_n + 216 - 1764) u_{n+5} + (216 + 1764) u_{n+6} + (-216 + 486) u_{n+7} + (126 - 486) u_{n+8}]$$

$$\text{Error order: 3, Error: } 9.96463548981715399 \times 10^{-10} \text{, New Error: } 1.4504424984611997 \times 10^{-10}$$
$$\text{Error order: 4, Error: } 1.4504424984611997 \times 10^{-10} \text{, New Error: } 1.45044020382432920 \times 10^{-10}$$
$$\text{Error order: 5, Error: } 1.45044020382432920 \times 10^{-10} \text{, New Error: } 1.450440078240248 \times 10^{-10}$$
$$\text{Error order: 6, Error: } 1.450440078240248 \times 10^{-10} \text{, New Error: } 1.4504400207974128 \times 10^{-10}$$
$$\text{Error order: 7, Error: } 1.4504400207974128 \times 10^{-10} \text{, New Error: } 1.4504400079371568 \times 10^{-10}$$

... Derivative Order: 3

... Derivative Order: 4

... Derivative Order: 5

... Derivative Order: 6

... Derivative Order: 7

... Derivative Order: 8

... Derivative Order: 9

... Derivative Order: 10

... Derivative Order: 11

... Derivative Order: 12

... Derivative Order: 13

... Derivative Order: 14

Error order: 20, Error: 9.02245399884568043 × 10⁻¹⁶⁷, New Error: 9.02241131679653630 × 10⁻¹⁶⁷

Error order: 20, Error: 9.02241131679653630 × 10⁻¹⁶⁷, New Error: 9.02241088202508182 × 10⁻¹⁶⁷

Error order: 20, Error: 9.02241088202508182 × 10⁻¹⁶⁷, New Error: 9.0224108877691515 × 10⁻¹⁶⁷

Error order: 20, Error: 9.0224108877691515 × 10⁻¹⁶⁷, New Error: 9.02241088776486562 × 10⁻¹⁶⁷

"... Derivative Order: 17 - x| = 1 ..."

0	1	2	3	4	5
-1	1	-1	2	-1	3
-2	1	-2	2	-2	3
-3	1	-3	2	-3	3
-4	1	-4	2	-4	3
-5	1	-5	2	-5	3

147351395610326859539	147351395610326859539	597864721355447156096	21805567981579718316157	82498781150994291460507	13386982668665846423741	32153018328687385115058	39167700249354945919564	1625707034522676226331	21118865627322069128951	341634189095023127589	21962949825735309737071
525580	525580	1932125	10414625	10414625	10414625	10414625	10414625	7728500	7728500	6509225	13138450
21805567981579718316157	597864721355447156096	131867541414421998219333	1318675414412998219333	507019674987898892196	1476460711088697708221	16737960795968071069	584198234072094579311	2863725261732836166071	27367982261054108185743	220109693808549049891101	3174238864311405931399
3864250	8500	5	25	25	5	325	325	4250	2125	7728500	7728500
13386982668665846423741	582498781150994291640507	147646071108869770822	507019674987898892196	17351251041217337174319	17351251041217337174319	1376647115957578889926	169818273122236159526261	1420310959528189262773	42839857630580643900271	872336504212820673657074	33280360452412322582003281
10414625	10414625	10414625	5	25	25	325	325	4250	2125	10414625	10414625
39167700249354945919564	32153018328687385115058	5841982340720944579311	1657396759789687617069	169818273122236159526261	1376647115957578889261	1409599380430731061949	1409599380430731061949	525781975640311622112	55939810660353102614	2004562470403532178471	2530521669803701068597571
10414625	10414625	325	65	65	325	325	325	325	325	10414625	10414625
2118865627322069128951	1625707034522676226331	27367982261054108185743	2863725261732836166071	42839857630580643900271	1420310959528189262773	55939810660353102614	525781975640311622112	69518189703153658123503	69518189703153658123503	44057290877586842674896	2669661287545019453617
7728500	7728500	2125	4250	325	325	325	325	6500	8500	1932125	3864250
2196294982573530973707	341634189095023127589	220109693808549049891101	7728500	3328036045241232258200328	87233650421232258200328	253052166980370106859757	2004562470403532178471	2669661287545019453617	44057290877586842674896	2396262959596466146371	25276900
10414625	10414625	7728500	7728500	10414625	10414625	10414625	10414625	3864250	1932125	3864250	25276900

$u^{17}(x) = \frac{1}{170799850} \text{det} [43659 (-10968919025843744325 + 10968919025843744325 \text{I}) u_{i+1} + (-121054633069518826496 + 2207576010624573066616 \text{I}) u_{i+2} + (21880895143902306564292 + 502866698632845410236 \text{I}) u_{i+3} + (12077910648337799417368 - 1471289509781033346254 \text{I}) u_{i+4} + (8292632089442065689 + 106907299848091732369 \text{I}) u_{i+5} + (-203451497151310460 + 653973614578614970 \text{I}) u_{i+6} + (2207576010624573066616 - 121054633069518826496 \text{I}) u_{i+7} + (606921726897763046687 + 606921726897763046687 \text{I}) u_{i+8} + (-793411525093424487269360 + 1155222733876151335162600 \text{I}) u_{i+9} + (99753133520682854507900 + 703216564997758105598420 \text{I}) u_{i+10} + (263610854660796529102658 - 50384568083852344991828 \text{I}) u_{i+11} + (114185902830741908219 - 16067862050442796928 \text{I}) u_{i+12} + (502866698632845410236 + 21880895143902306564292 \text{I}) u_{i+13} + (-115222733876151335162600 - 793411525093424487269360 \text{I}) u_{i+14} + (2084290101078126564809680 + 2084290101078126564809680 \text{I}) u_{i+15} + (-165711622351910947972189920 + (-165711622351910947972189920 + 31321321934364081078320 \text{I}) u_{i+16} + (-165711622351910947972189920 + 31321321934364081078320 \text{I}) u_{i+17} + (165711622351910947972189920 \text{I}) u_{i+18} + (16924365000892437951303180 + 16924365000892437951303180 \text{I}) u_{i+19} + (-6329013672188164611571840 + 673362261365566457873480 \text{I}) u_{i+20} + (-6329013672188164611571840 + 673362261365566457873480 \text{I}) u_{i+21} + (-5038456808385234499328 - 263610854660796529102658 \text{I}) u_{i+22} + (-5038456808385234499328 + 263610854660796529102658 \text{I}) u_{i+23} + (515677091410202537817140 + 85483792695832400294900 \text{I}) u_{i+24} + (673362261365566457873480 - 6329013672188164611571840 \text{I}) u_{i+25} + (-793411525093424487269360 + 1155222733876151335162600 \text{I}) u_{i+26} + (-99753133520682854507900 + 703216564997758105598420 \text{I}) u_{i+27} + (263610854660796529102658 - 5038456808385234499328 \text{I}) u_{i+28} + (114185902830741908219 - 16067862050442796928 \text{I}) u_{i+29} + (502866698632845410236 + 21880895143902306564292 \text{I}) u_{i+30} + (-115222733876151335162600 - 793411525093424487269360 \text{I}) u_{i+31} + (2084290101078126564809680 + 2084290101078126564809680 \text{I}) u_{i+32} + (-165711622351910947972189920 + (-165711622351910947972189920 + 31321321934364081078320 \text{I}) u_{i+33} + (-165711622351910947972189920 + 31321321934364081078320 \text{I}) u_{i+34} + (165711622351910947972189920 \text{I}) u_{i+35} + (16924365000892437951303180 + 16924365000892437951303180 \text{I}) u_{i+36} + (-6329013672188164611571840 + 673362261365566457873480 \text{I}) u_{i+37} + (-6329013672188164611571840 + 673362261365566457873480 \text{I}) u_{i+38} + (-5038456808385234499328 - 263610854660796529102658 \text{I}) u_{i+39} + (-5038456808385234499328 + 263610854660796529102658 \text{I}) u_{i+40} + (515677091410202537817140 + 85483792695832400294900 \text{I}) u_{i+41} + (673362261365566457873480 - 6329013672188164611571840 \text{I}) u_{i+42} + (-793411525093424487269360 + 1155222733876151335162600 \text{I}) u_{i+43} + (-99753133520682854507900 + 703216564997758105598420 \text{I}) u_{i+44} + (263610854660796529102658 - 5038456808385234499328 \text{I}) u_{i+45} + (114185902830741908219 - 16067862050442796928 \text{I}) u_{i+46} + (502866698632845410236 + 21880895143902306564292 \text{I}) u_{i+47} + (-115222733876151335162600 - 793411525093424487269360 \text{I}) u_{i+48} + (2084290101078126564809680 + 2084290101078126564809680 \text{I}) u_{i+49} + (-165711622351910947972189920 + (-165711622351910947972189920 + 31321321934364081078320 \text{I}) u_{i+50} + (-165711622351910947972189920 + 31321321934364081078320 \text{I}) u_{i+51} + (165711622351910947972189920 \text{I}) u_{i+52} + (16924365000892437951303180 + 16924365000892437951303180 \text{I}) u_{i+53} + (-6329013672188164611571840 + 673362261365566457873480 \text{I}) u_{i+54} + (-6329013672188164611571840 + 673362261365566457873480 \text{I}) u_{i+55} + (-5038456808385234499328 - 263610854660796529102658 \text{I}) u_{i+56} + (-5038456808385234499328 + 263610854660796529102658 \text{I}) u_{i+57} + (515677091410202537817140 + 85483792695832400294900 \text{I}) u_{i+58} + (673362261365566457873480 - 6329013672188164611571840 \text{I}) u_{i+59} + (-793411525093424487269360 + 1155222733876151335162600 \text{I}) u_{i+60} + (-99753133520682854507900 + 703216564997758105598420 \text{I}) u_{i+61} + (263610854660796529102658 - 5038456808385234499328 \text{I}) u_{i+62} + (114185902830741908219 - 16067862050442796928 \text{I}) u_{i+63} + (502866698632845410236 + 21880895143902306564292 \text{I}) u_{i+64} + (-115222733876151335162600 - 793411525093424487269360 \text{I}) u_{i+65} + (2084290101078126564809680 + 2084290101078126564809680 \text{I}) u_{i+66} + (-165711622351910947972189920 + (-165711622351910947972189920 + 31321321934364081078320 \text{I}) u_{i+67} + (-165711622351910947972189920 + 31321321934364081078320 \text{I}) u_{i+68} + (165711622351910947972189920 \text{I}) u_{i+69} + (16924365000892437951303180 + 16924365000892437951303180 \text{I}) u_{i+70} + (-6329013672188164611571840 + 673362261365566457873480 \text{I}) u_{i+71} + (-6329013672188164611571840 + 673362261365566457873480 \text{I}) u_{i+72} + (-5038456808385234499328 - 263610854660796529102658 \text{I}) u_{i+73} + (-5038456808385234499328 + 263610854660796529102658 \text{I}) u_{i+74} + (515677091410202537817140 + 85483792695832400294900 \text{I}) u_{i+75} + (673362261365566457873480 - 6329013672188164611571840 \text{I}) u_{i+76} + (-793411525093424487269360 + 1155222733876151335162600 \text{I}) u_{i+77} + (-99753133520682854507900 + 703216564997758105598420 \text{I}) u_{i+78} + (263610854660796529102658 - 5038456808385234499328 \text{I}) u_{i+79} + (114185902830741908219 - 16067862050442796928 \text{I}) u_{i+80} + (502866698632845410236 + 21880895143902306564292 \text{I}) u_{i+81} + (-115222733876151335162600 - 793411525093424487269360 \text{I}) u_{i+82} + (2084290101078126564809680 + 2084290101078126564809680 \text{I}) u_{i+83} + (-165711622351910947972189920 + (-165711622351910947972189920 + 31321321934364081078320 \text{I}) u_{i+84} + (-165711622351910947972189920 + 31321321934364081078320 \text{I}) u_{i+85} + (165711622351910947972189920 \text{I}) u_{i+86} + (16924365000892437951303180 + 16924365000892437951303180 \text{I}) u_{i+87} + (-6329013672188164611571840 + 673362261365566457873480 \text{I}) u_{i+88} + (-6329013672188164611571840 + 673362261365566457873480 \text{I}) u_{i+89} + (-5038456808385234499328 - 263610854660796529102658 \text{I}) u_{i+90} + (-5038456808385234499328 + 263610854660796529102658 \text{I}) u_{i+91} + (515677091410202537817140 + 85483792695832400294900 \text{I}) u_{i+92} + (673362261365566457873480 - 6329013672188164611571840 \text{I}) u_{i+93} + (-793411525093424487269360 + 1155222733876151335162600 \text{I}) u_{i+94} + (-99753133520682854507900 + 703216564997758105598420 \text{I}) u_{i+95} + (263610854660796529102658 - 5038456808385234499328 \text{I}) u_{i+96} + (114185902830741908219 - 16067862050442796928 \text{I}) u_{i+97} + (502866698632845410236 + 21880895143902306564292 \text{I}) u_{i+98} + (-115222733876151335162600 - 793411525093424487269360 \text{I}) u_{i+99} + (2084290101078126564809680 + 2084290101078126564809680 \text{I}) u_{i+100} + (-165711622351910947972189920 + (-165711622351910947972189920 + 31321321934364081078320 \text{I}) u_{i+101} + (-165711622351910947972189920 + 31321321934364081078320 \text{I}) u_{i+102} + (165711622351910947972189920 \text{I}) u_{i+103} + (16924365000892437951303180 + 16924365000892437951303180 \text{I}) u_{i+104} + (-6329013672188164611571840 + 673362261365566457873480 \text{I}) u_{i+105} + (-6329013672188164611571840 + 673362261365566457873480 \text{I}) u_{i+106} + (-5038456808385234499328 - 263610854660796529102658 \text{I}) u_{i+107} + (-5038456808385234499328 + 263610854660796529102658 \text{I}) u_{i+108} + (515677091410202537817140 + 85483792695832400294900 \text{I}) u_{i+109} + (673362261365566457873480 - 6329013672188164611571840 \text{I}) u_{i+110} + (-793411525093424487269360 + 1155222733876151335162600 \text{I}) u_{i+111} + (-99753133520682854507900 + 703216564997758105598420 \text{I}) u_{i+112} + (263610854660796529102658 - 5038456808385234499328 \text{I}) u_{i+113} + (114185902830741908219 - 16067862050442796928 \text{I}) u_{i+114} + (502866698632845410236 + 21880895143902306564292 \text{I}) u_{i+115} + (-115222733876151335162600 - 793411525093424487269360 \text{I}) u_{i+116} + (2084290101078126564809680 + 2084290101078126564809680 \text{I}) u_{i+117} + (-165711622351910947972189920 + (-165711622351910947972189920 + 31321321934364081078320 \text{I}) u_{i+118} + (-165711622351910947972189920 + 31321321934364081078320 \text{I}) u_{i+119} + (165711622351910947972189920 \text{I}) u_{i+120} + (16924365000892437951303180 + 16924365000892437951303180 \text{I}) u_{i+121} + (-6329013672188164611571840 + 673362261365566457873480 \text{I}) u_{i+122} + (-6329013672188164611571840 + 673362261365566457873480 \text{I}) u_{i+123} + (-5038456808385234499328 - 263610854660796529102658 \text{I}) u_{i+124} + (-5038456808385234499328 + 263610854660796529102658 \text{I}) u_{i+125} + (515677091410202537817140 + 85483792695832400294900 \text{I}) u_{i+126} + (673362261365566457873480 - 6329013672188164611571840 \text{I}) u_{i+127} + (-793411525093424487269360 + 1155222733876151335162600 \text{I}) u_{i+128} + (-99753133520682854507900 + 703216564997758105598420 \text{I}) u_{i+129} + (263610854660796529102658 - 5038456808385234499328 \text{I}) u_{i+130} + (114185902830741908219 - 16067862050442796928 \text{I}) u_{i+131} + (502866698632845410236 + 21880895143902306564292 \text{I}) u_{i+132} + (-115222733876151335162600 - 793411525093424487269360 \text{I}) u_{i+133} + (2084290101078126564809680 + 2084290101078126564809680 \text{I}) u_{i+134} + (-165711622351910947972189920 + (-165711622351910947972189920 + 31321321934364081078320 \text{I}) u_{i+135} + (-165711622351910947972189920 + 31321321934364081078320 \text{I}) u_{i+136} + (165711622351910947972189920 \text{I}) u_{i+137} + (16924365000892437951303180 + 169243650$

Table with mathematical expressions involving u(x) and various numerical coefficients and indices.

Equation for u(x) with a denominator and a large polynomial numerator.

Series of numerical coefficients and indices for u(x) values.

Large block of numerical coefficients and indices for u(x) values, including error orders.

Equation for u(x) with a denominator and a large polynomial numerator.

Series of numerical coefficients and indices for u(x) values.

Equation for u(x) with a denominator and a large polynomial numerator.

Table with numerical coefficients and indices for u(x) values.

Table with numerical coefficients and indices for u(x) values.

Table with numerical coefficients and indices for u(x) values.

Equation for u(x) with a denominator and a large polynomial numerator.

Series of numerical coefficients and indices for u(x) values.

Equation for u(x) with a denominator and a large polynomial numerator.

Table with numerical coefficients and indices for u(x) values.

Table with numerical coefficients and indices for u(x) values.

Table with numerical coefficients and indices for u(x) values.

Equation for u(x) with a denominator and a large polynomial numerator.

Series of numerical coefficients and indices for u(x) values.

Equation for u(x) with a denominator and a large polynomial numerator.

Series of numerical coefficients and indices for u(x) values.

Equation for u(x) with a denominator and a large polynomial numerator.

Series of numerical coefficients and indices for u(x) values.

Equation for u(x) with a denominator and a large polynomial numerator.

Series of numerical coefficients and indices for u(x) values.

Equation for u(x) with a denominator and a large polynomial numerator.

Series of numerical coefficients and indices for u(x) values.

u(x) = ...

u(x) = ...

u(x) = ...

Table with 7 columns, containing numerical data points.

u(x) = ...

u(x) = ...

u(x) = ...

Table with 7 columns, containing numerical data points.

u(x) = ...

u(x) = ...

u(x) = ...

u(x) = ...

Table with 7 columns, containing numerical data points.

u(x) = ...

u(x) = ...

u(x) = ...

Table with 7 columns, containing numerical data points.

u(x) = ...

u(x) = ...

Table with 7 columns, containing numerical data points.

u(x) = ...

u(x) = ...

u(x) = ...

Derivative Order: 9 - x | -1 - ...

Table with 6 columns and 10 rows of numerical data.

Derivative Order: 10 - x | -1 - ...

Table with 6 columns and 10 rows of numerical data.

Derivative Order: 11 - x | -1 - ...

Table with 6 columns and 10 rows of numerical data.

Derivative Order: 12 - x | -1 - ...

Table with 6 columns and 10 rows of numerical data.

Derivative Order: 13 - x | -1 - ...

Table with 6 columns and 10 rows of numerical data.

Derivative Order: 14 - x | -1 - ...

Table with 6 columns and 10 rows of numerical data.

Derivative Order: 15 - x | -1 - ...

Table with 6 columns and 10 rows of numerical data.

(+182732593591089549382396756000 + 374155533257409177132863492001) u_{n+2n+1} + (1886783003395780481067521282000 + 972862066857354818808979146000) u_{n+2n} + ...

Table with 10 columns and 10 rows of numerical data. The first row contains values like 289740334083208637133254665, 28974033340820863871332546651, etc. The second row contains values like 22304040954822513154148341648, 22304040949822513154148341648, etc. The table continues with similar patterns of numbers.

... Derivative Order: 1 - x | -1 ...

Table with 10 columns and 10 rows of numerical data. The first row contains values like 289740334083208637133254665, 28974033340820863871332546651, etc. The second row contains values like 22304040954822513154148341648, 22304040949822513154148341648, etc. The table continues with similar patterns of numbers.

(-335241892509609101435948995722875 + 358214892509609101435948995722875) u_{n+1} + (100416646975185174929618308934880000 + 16338701449601049856034932387046000) u_{n+2} + ...

Error order: 80, Error: 5.2076352723113710 x 10^-100, New Error: 8.10754574893366606 x 10^-104

... Derivative Order: 1 - x | -1 ...

(-1 + 1) u_{n+2n+1} - 8 u_{n+2n} + (1 - 1) u_{n+2n+1} - 8 u_{n+2n} + (1 - 1) u_{n+2n+1} - 8 u_{n+2n} + ...

Error order: 80, Error: 7.4449827184800164 x 10^-100, New Error: 7.4449827184800164 x 10^-100

... Derivative Order: 1 - x | -1 ...

(-1 + 1) u_{n+2n+1} - 8 u_{n+2n} + (1 - 1) u_{n+2n+1} - 8 u_{n+2n} + (1 - 1) u_{n+2n+1} - 8 u_{n+2n} + ...

Error order: 80, Error: 4.86024494706670188 x 10^-100, New Error: 4.86024494706670188 x 10^-100

(-1 + 1) u_{n+2n+1} - 8 u_{n+2n} + (1 - 1) u_{n+2n+1} - 8 u_{n+2n} + (1 - 1) u_{n+2n+1} - 8 u_{n+2n} + ...

Error order: 80, Error: 2.2248756926052283 x 10^-100, New Error: 2.2248756926052283 x 10^-100

(-1 + 1) u_{n+2n+1} - 8 u_{n+2n} + (1 - 1) u_{n+2n+1} - 8 u_{n+2n} + (1 - 1) u_{n+2n+1} - 8 u_{n+2n} + ...

Error order: 80, Error: 2.960196361750610931 x 10^-100, New Error: 2.960196361750610931 x 10^-100

Error order: 24, Error: 6.0232323141179150557 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 6.0232323141179232849 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order: 24, Error: 6.0232323141179232849 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 6.0232323141179232849 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order: 24, Error: 6.0232323141179232849 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 6.0232323141179232849 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order: 24, Error: 6.0232323141179232849 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 6.0232323141179232849 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order: 24, Error: 6.0232323141179232849 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 6.0232323141179232849 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰

$$u^{\mu}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{\Omega_{\mathbf{x}}^{\mu}} \left[\dots \right]$$

Centered
Error order: 24, Error: 1.78463157203761768 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 1.78463157203761768 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order: 24, Error: 1.78463157203761768 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 1.78463157203761768 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order: 24, Error: 1.78463157203761768 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 1.78463157203761768 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order: 24, Error: 1.78463157203761768 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 1.78463157203761768 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰

$$u^{\mu}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{\Omega_{\mathbf{x}}^{\mu}} \left[\dots \right]$$

Centered
Error order: 24, Error: 2.363915228610752683 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 2.363915228610752683 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order: 24, Error: 2.363915228610752683 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 2.363915228610752683 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order: 24, Error: 2.363915228610752683 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 2.363915228610752683 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order: 24, Error: 2.363915228610752683 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 2.363915228610752683 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰

$$u^{\mu}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{\Omega_{\mathbf{x}}^{\mu}} \left[\dots \right]$$

Centered
Error order: 24, Error: 2.94031222969534521 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 2.94031222969534521 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order: 24, Error: 2.94031222969534521 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 2.94031222969534521 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order: 24, Error: 2.94031222969534521 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 2.94031222969534521 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order: 24, Error: 2.94031222969534521 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 2.94031222969534521 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰

$$u^{\mu}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{\Omega_{\mathbf{x}}^{\mu}} \left[\dots \right]$$

Centered
Error order: 24, Error: 8.8751020983617419 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 8.8751020983617419 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order: 24, Error: 8.8751020983617419 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 8.8751020983617419 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order: 24, Error: 8.8751020983617419 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 8.8751020983617419 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰
Error order: 24, Error: 8.8751020983617419 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰, New Error: 8.8751020983617419 x 10⁻¹⁰⁰

... Derivative Order: 13 - x|1 - ...

Matrix of coefficients for Derivative Order 13

Matrix of numerical values for Derivative Order 13

Equation for u(x) with coefficients and error terms for Derivative Order 13

Error order: 12, Error: 6.821660539990698880 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 6.821660539990698880 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 12, Error: 6.821660539990698880 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 6.821660539990698880 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 12, Error: 6.821660539990698880 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 6.821660539990698880 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 12, Error: 6.821660539990698880 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 6.821660539990698880 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

... Derivative Order: 14 - x|1 - ...

Matrix of coefficients for Derivative Order 14

Matrix of numerical values for Derivative Order 14

Equation for u(x) with coefficients and error terms for Derivative Order 14

Error order: 12, Error: 3.6658700890521640731 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 3.6658700890521640731 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 12, Error: 3.6658700890521640731 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 3.6658700890521640731 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 12, Error: 3.6658700890521640731 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 3.6658700890521640731 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 12, Error: 3.6658700890521640731 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 3.6658700890521640731 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

... Derivative Order: 15 - x|1 - ...

Matrix of coefficients for Derivative Order 15

Matrix of numerical values for Derivative Order 15

Equation for u(x) with coefficients and error terms for Derivative Order 15

Error order: 12, Error: 2.032529435047733827 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 2.032529435047733827 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 12, Error: 2.032529435047733827 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 2.032529435047733827 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 12, Error: 2.032529435047733827 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 2.032529435047733827 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 12, Error: 2.032529435047733827 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 2.032529435047733827 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

... Derivative Order: 16 - x|1 - ...

Matrix of coefficients for Derivative Order 16

Matrix of numerical values for Derivative Order 16

Equation for u(x) with coefficients and error terms for Derivative Order 16

Error order: 12, Error: 1.1591271371815053237 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 1.1591271371815053237 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 12, Error: 1.1591271371815053237 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 1.1591271371815053237 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 12, Error: 1.1591271371815053237 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 1.1591271371815053237 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 12, Error: 1.1591271371815053237 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 1.1591271371815053237 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

... Derivative Order: 17 - x|1 - ...

Matrix of coefficients for Derivative Order 17

Matrix of numerical values for Derivative Order 17

Equation for u(x) with coefficients and error terms for Derivative Order 17

Error order: 8, Error: 6.8252320900200118095 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 6.8252320900200118095 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 8, Error: 6.8252320900200118095 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 6.8252320900200118095 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 8, Error: 6.8252320900200118095 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 6.8252320900200118095 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 8, Error: 6.8252320900200118095 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 6.8252320900200118095 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

... Derivative Order: 18 - x|1 - ...

Matrix of coefficients for Derivative Order 18

Matrix of numerical values for Derivative Order 18

Equation for u(x) with coefficients and error terms for Derivative Order 18

Error order: 8, Error: 4.7157292192676267884 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 4.7157292192676267884 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 8, Error: 4.7157292192676267884 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 4.7157292192676267884 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 8, Error: 4.7157292192676267884 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 4.7157292192676267884 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

Error order: 8, Error: 4.7157292192676267884 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 4.7157292192676267884 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴

u(x) = ... (7 - 35321530888897 ...)

Derivative Order: 11 - x|1 - ...

Table with 11 columns and 11 rows of numerical values.

u(x) = ... (7 - 35321530888897 + 353281530888897 ...)

Derivative Order: 12 - x|1 - ...

Table with 11 columns and 11 rows of numerical values.

u(x) = ... (7 - 35321530888897 + 353281530888897 + 353281530888897 ...)

Derivative Order: 13 - x|1 - ...

Table with 11 columns and 11 rows of numerical values.

u(x) = ... (7 - 4952659901551761 ...)

Derivative Order: 13 - x|1 - ...

Table with 11 columns and 11 rows of numerical values.

u(x) = ... (7 - 4952659901551761 + 50655759745721407200 ...)

Derivative Order: 13 - x|1 - ...

Table with 11 columns and 11 rows of numerical values.

u(x) = ... (7 - 4952659901551761 + 50655759745721407200 + 50655759745721407200 ...)

Derivative Order: 13 - x|1 - ...

Table with 11 columns and 11 rows of numerical values.

u(x) = ... (7 - 115897100657 + 115897100657 ...)

Derivative Order: 14 - x|1 - ...

Table with 11 columns and 11 rows of numerical values.

u(x) = ... (7 - 115897100657 + 115897100657 + 115897100657 ...)

Derivative Order: 15 - x|1 - ...

Table with 11 columns and 11 rows of numerical values.

u(x) = ... (7 - 115897100657 + 115897100657 + 115897100657 + 115897100657 ...)

Derivative Order: 15 - x|1 - ...

Table with 11 columns and 11 rows of numerical values.

u(x) = ... (7 - 115897100657 + 115897100657 + 115897100657 + 115897100657 + 115897100657 ...)

Derivative Order: 15 - x|1 - ...

Table with 11 columns and 11 rows of numerical values.

